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Energy and entropy in critical systems with impurities

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Abstract

In this thesis we study two-dimensional CFTs with an interface insertion along the time axis. In particular, the goal is to prove

$$c_{eff} \geq c_{LR}$$

proposed in [17], where c_{eff} and c_{LR} are two constants related to the entanglement entropy of a subsystem and the energy transmission across the interface. Our strategy is to explicitly calculate the Casini bound [11] for this specific set-up and in this way relate the two constants.

We reproduce some known results on defect CFTs, energy transmission and entanglement and Rényi entropies in the vacuum. We then introduce a new operator, the defect twist operator, to encode the entangling surface as it approaches the interface. We find its scaling dimension as a function of c_{eff} and we compute the entanglement entropy for an excited state through the expectation value of the twist operators. We therefore obtain the lhs of the Casini bound, which depends on c_{eff} , while the right-hand side is left for future work.

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1 Introduction

Two-dimensional conformal field theories have been studied for many years. [12, 14, 8, 25, 3, 30, 15] They are an important set of theories because conformal symmetry constrains them more than just Lorentzian symmetry, as the conformal generators are holomorphic functions and can be expanded in an infinite sum of operators, which means an infinite number of constraints on the theory. CFTs are used to describe critical systems, as they are scale-invariant, and are used in theoretical condensed matter physics [23] and string theory [13, 24].

More recently, the introduction of a defect in the theory has gained more attention. [5, 19] Conformal defects can describe impurities in a condensed matter system, interfaces, and boundaries. They are studied as extended operators, and their presence changes the correlation functions and the symmetry group.

In this work, we aim to study two two-dimensional CFTs communicating through an interface placed at $x = 0$. In particular, we focus on the energy transmitted across the interface after an excitation is produced on the left, and on the entanglement entropy of the spatial section of the right CFT both in the vacuum and the excited state.

The energy transmission coefficient is proportional to a constant c_{LR} , which defines the two-point function of a stress tensor on the left and a stress tensor on the right. [20, 26] The entanglement entropy, which without defects depends on the central charge of the theory c , is proportional to another new constant c_{eff} . [29, 9, 17]

It has already been shown that [18, 20]

$$c_{LR} \leq \min(c_L, c_R) \quad c_{eff} \leq \min(c_L, c_R)$$

Recently, it has been proposed that [17]

$$c_{eff} \geq c_{LR} .$$

It has been proven for specific CFTs, but not in general.

Our goal is to demonstrate it. To do so, we study another bound, which is valid for every QFT and states

$$S(\rho_V) - S(\rho_V^0) \leq \langle K_V \rangle - \langle K_V \rangle_0 ,$$

where S is the entanglement entropy associated with a region of space V described by the reduced density matrix ρ_V , and K is the modular Hamiltonian of V , which is a sort of generalized energy. The subscript "0" indicates that the quantity is evaluated in the vacuum. [11] We then need to evaluate the entanglement entropy for an excited state in an interface CFT, and the corresponding modular Hamiltonian.

For the first quantity, we define a defect twist operator, find its scaling dimension and evaluate the entanglement entropy as the two-point function of the defect twist fields in the excited state. We find that this quantity does indeed depend on c_{eff} , which supports our thesis.

The modular Hamiltonian still needs to be calculated and is left for future work.

Figure 1: Conformal transformations preserve angles. CFTs are the theories invariant under these transformations.

2 Defect Conformal Field Theory

In this section, generalities about CFTs, and especially in two dimensions, are reviewed. It is discussed what inserting a defect means and what consequences this operation has on the theory.

2.1 Conformal Field Theory

Conformal Field Theories (CFTs) are a special subset of Quantum Field Theories (QFTs), which are invariant under more transformations than the Lorentzian ones. Indeed, a CFT is defined to be invariant under any transformation which preserves angles, so as well as translations, rotations, and boosts, there are also dilations and special conformal transformations that must be considered [12, 14, 8, 3, 30, 28].

In the following, we justify where they come from and we derive their corresponding generators. The group that realizes these transformations is called the conformal group, and the theory is said to be invariant under conformal symmetry.

Let us build the conformal group. Given two vectors v^μ and w^μ and given a metric $g_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu$, we require

$$\frac{g_{\mu\nu}v^\mu w^\nu}{\sqrt{g_{\mu\nu}v^\mu v^\nu} \sqrt{g_{\mu\nu}w^\mu w^\nu}} \quad \text{invariant} \quad (1)$$

which means that all the coordinate transformations that lead to

$$g'_{\mu\nu}(x'^\lambda) = \Omega(x^\lambda)g_{\mu\nu}(x^\lambda) \quad (2)$$

are allowed.

Poincaré transformations leave $ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu$ invariant, so that $\Omega(x) = 1$ above. They

are a subset of all the possible transformations and this means that a CFT is more symmetric than a general QFT. This is remarkable since the presence of more symmetries goes together with the presence of more constraints on the theory, which then give us more information about the theory itself ¹.

To derive all the allowed transformations, let us start from an infinitesimal transformation. Let us consider $x^\mu \rightarrow x'^\mu = x^\mu + \epsilon^\mu(x)$, $\epsilon^\mu(x) \ll 1$. The change in the metric is

$$g'_{\mu\nu}(x'^\lambda) = g_{\alpha\beta}(x^\lambda) \frac{\partial x^\alpha}{\partial x'^\mu} \frac{\partial x^\beta}{\partial x'^\nu} = g_{\alpha\beta}(x^\lambda) (\delta_\mu^\alpha - \partial_\mu \epsilon^\alpha(x^\lambda)) (\delta_\nu^\beta - \partial_\nu \epsilon^\beta(x^\lambda)). \quad (3)$$

We can assume $g_{\mu\nu}(x) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ without loss of generality.

It is always possible to write the transformation of the metric as the action of a general element of the symmetry group $\Omega(x) = e^{-\sigma(x)}$ on the metric itself, and for small deformations it can be approximated by $\Omega(x) \approx \mathbb{1} - \sigma(x)$. Then $g'_{\mu\nu}(x) \approx (\mathbb{1} - \sigma(x))\eta_{\mu\nu}$ and at first order the above expression becomes

$$\partial_\mu \epsilon_\nu(x^\lambda) + \partial_\nu \epsilon_\mu(x^\lambda) = \eta_{\mu\nu} \sigma(x^\lambda). \quad (4)$$

By contracting the above expression with the flat metric, it is obtained that $\sigma(x^\lambda) = \frac{2}{d} \partial \cdot \epsilon$. Then after some algebraic manipulation, it becomes

$$(\eta_{\mu\nu} \square + (d-2) \partial_\mu \partial_\nu) (\partial \cdot \epsilon) = 0. \quad (5)$$

In $d > 2$, the most general solution is

$$\partial_\alpha \partial_\beta \partial_\gamma \epsilon_\mu(x^\lambda) = 0. \quad (6)$$

The functions allowed with respect to this constraint are related to the generators of translations, dilations, rotations, and special conformal transformations. The latter are transformations that preserve angles, and permit one to move the point at infinity. It can be shown that any infinitesimal special conformal transformation can be obtained as the application of a translation, an inversion, and another translation. The inversion $x^\mu \rightarrow x'^\mu = x^\mu / (x^\nu x_\nu)$ must be highlighted, since it is an important conformal transformation but disconnected from the identity of the conformal group². The generators of the conformal group are then, respectively,

$$\begin{cases} P_\mu = i \partial_\mu \\ D = i x^\mu \partial_\mu \\ M^{\mu\nu} = i(x^\mu \partial^\nu - x^\nu \partial^\mu) \\ K^\mu = i(2x^\mu x^\nu \partial_\nu - x^2 \partial_\mu), \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

which are of maximum second degree in x^μ to satisfy equation 6 and have non-trivial relations among the terms in $M^{\mu\nu}$ and K^μ due to equation 4.

¹This is the idea underlying the conformal bootstrap program[25]

²It cannot be obtained by the exponentiation of infinitesimal transformations.

In two dimensions, equation (4) reads as the Cauchy-Riemann conditions for the analyticity of a function in the complex plane. We will spend a few more words on two-dimensional CFTs in the next sections.

Since dilations are also included, these types of theories are invariant under scale transformations, which means they do not have a typical scale. This characteristic makes them particularly useful for describing critical systems, where the expectation values of operators do not decay exponentially but polynomially, and in condensed matter physics it translates into the fact that the same patterns and structures arise when the system is observed at any scale.

Another reason why two-dimensional CFTs are studied today is the following. It is possible to see that the generators of the conformal transformations on a space with metric signature (p, q) satisfy the algebra of $SO(p+1, q+1)$, so they can be realized as generators of Lorentz transformations on a space with metric signature $(p+1, q+1)$.

As a consequence, conformal field theories in two dimensions become really interesting, since they can be linked to the Minkowski physical space $SO(1, 3)$. This is the idea behind so-called "celestial holography", and it relates gravitational scattering processes to correlators of a $2d$ CFT living at the boundary of the $(3+1)d$ space [22].

2.2 Two Dimensions

In two dimensions, the constraint on the generator in 4 reads

$$\begin{cases} \partial_1 \epsilon_1 = \partial_2 \epsilon_2 \\ \partial_1 \epsilon_2 = -\partial_2 \epsilon_1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

which are the Cauchy-Riemann conditions for a complex function to be analytic. Defining $z := x_1 + ix_2$ and $\bar{z} := x_1 - ix_2$ on the complex plane \mathbb{C} , a general solution of the Cauchy-Riemann conditions is $a \epsilon(z) + b \bar{\epsilon}(\bar{z})$, where $\epsilon(z) = \epsilon_1(z) + i\epsilon_2(z)$ and $\bar{\epsilon}(\bar{z}) = \epsilon_1(\bar{z}) - i\epsilon_2(\bar{z})$ are holomorphic and antiholomorphic functions, so that $\partial\epsilon/\partial\bar{z} = 0 = \partial\bar{\epsilon}/\partial z$.

Analytic functions can be expanded in a Laurent series

$$\epsilon(z) = \sum_n a_n z^n = \sum_n (-a_n l_{n-1}) z \quad l_n := -z^{n+1} \partial_z \quad (9)$$

and similarly for $\bar{\epsilon}(\bar{z})$ with coefficients \bar{a}_n and operators \bar{l}_n . This means that there are infinite generators l_n and \bar{l}_n for conformal transformations on the complex plane. These operators factorize into two independent subalgebras. Indeed, the commutators are

$$\begin{cases} [l_n, \bar{l}_m] = 0 \\ [l_n, l_m] = (n-m)l_{n+m} \\ [\bar{l}_n, \bar{l}_m] = (n-m)\bar{l}_{n+m} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

and define two separate classical Virasoro algebras.

Now that the generators are well defined, it would be natural to exponentiate them and find

the corresponding Lie group, whose elements act on \mathbb{C} . It turns out that in this case, it is not possible to find the corresponding group via the exponential map. Indeed, this algebra is well defined only locally, and the generators are not globally well defined on the Riemann sphere [14]. Singularities arise when $z \rightarrow 0$ for $n < -1$, and when $z \rightarrow \infty$ for $n > 1$ ³. The conformal symmetry is then studied at the algebraic level.

Actually, there exists a closed subalgebra in the Virasoro algebra, composed of l_{-1} , l_0 , and l_{+1} , satisfying

$$[l_i, l_i] = 0 \quad [l_{\pm 1}, l_0] = l_{\pm 1} \quad [l_1, l_{-1}] = l_0. \quad (11)$$

If exponentiated, it gives the small conformal subgroup $SL(2, \mathbb{C})$, which is invertible. Its realization consists of the set of fractional linear functions⁴. To eliminate the ambiguity of the sign, $SL(2, \mathbb{C})/\mathbb{Z}_2$ must be considered. This is isomorphic to $SO(1, 3)$: the six conformal generators of the small conformal group (three holomorphic, three antiholomorphic) are related to $SO(1, 3)$ such that $\{l_{-1}, \bar{l}_{-1}\}$ generate the translations, $(l_0 + \bar{l}_0)$ generates dilations, $(l_0 - \bar{l}_0)$ generates rotations, and $\{l_1, \bar{l}_1\}$ generate special conformal transformations. The rest of the total conformal algebra generates all the possible conformal transformations, which cannot be written explicitly as a finite action on the coordinates.

Consider an operator that is an eigenvector of l_0 and \bar{l}_0 , with corresponding eigenvalues h and \bar{h} . This means that, under a rescaling of the system performed by $(l_0 + \bar{l}_0)$, the value of the associated observable is rescaled by a power of $h + \bar{h}$. We then define the scaling dimension of the field as $\Delta = h + \bar{h}$. Similarly, its spin will be $s = h - \bar{h}$, as it describes how the field responds to a rotation of the coordinates. For a scalar field, $h = \bar{h}$ and $s = 0$.

A standard way to work with these theories is to define a new set of coordinates, obtained via an exponentiation of the time and space coordinates.

Let us denote ζ_0 and ζ_1 as the time and space coordinates, respectively. Consider the (anti)holomorphic maps $z = e^{\zeta_0 + i\zeta_1}$ and $\bar{z} = e^{\zeta_0 - i\zeta_1}$. Now ζ_0 denotes the radius in the z -plane, so that the vacuum state $|0\rangle$, which is obtained at $\zeta_0 = -\infty$, is placed at $z = 0$. Then increasing the time ζ_0 corresponds to increasing the radius of z , so the time-evolution Hamiltonian is mapped into the dilation operator $l_0 + \bar{l}_0$. This procedure is called "radial quantization". Another consequence is that the time-ordering prescription now becomes a radial-ordering prescription, which is

$$R(A(z)B(w)) = \begin{cases} A(z)B(w) & \text{if } |z| > |w| \\ B(w)A(z) & \text{if } |w| > |z| \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

and constant-time integrals are translated into equal-radius closed integrals. As the space coordinate is compactified, this map is used to study (1+1)-dimensional finite systems with

³This result is obtained via the inversion map $z = -1/w$, so that $l_n = -z^{n+1}\partial_z = -w^{-n-1}|\partial z/\partial w|\partial_w = -w^{-n-1}\partial_w$.

⁴Also, $\{l_{-n}, l_0, l_n\}$ forms a closed subalgebra, but the corresponding group is not invertible.

periodic boundary conditions. It is equivalent to mapping it onto a cylinder, where the space dimension is mapped to the angle of the cylinder, while time runs along its height.

2.2.1 Primary fields and the Operator Product Expansion

A scalar field is defined as "quasi-primary" if, under a conformal transformation, it changes as

$$\phi(x) \xrightarrow{x \rightarrow x'(x)} \left| \frac{\partial x'}{\partial x} \right|^{\Delta_\phi/d} \phi(x'). \quad (13)$$

These transformations are remapping the space, so the physics must not be affected by them. Thus, when evaluating the expectation values (or correlation functions) of the fields, these must be invariant objects. We therefore have Ward identities that derive from this constraint. The main results are

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \phi(x) \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle \phi_1(x_1) \phi_2(x_2) \rangle &= \frac{1}{|x_1 - x_2|^{2\Delta}} = \frac{1}{r_{12}^{2\Delta}} \quad \text{iff } \Delta_1 = \Delta_2 \\ \langle \phi_1(x_1) \phi_2(x_2) \phi_3(x_3) \rangle &= \frac{c_{123}}{r_{12}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 - \Delta_3} r_{13}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_3 - \Delta_2} r_{23}^{\Delta_2 + \Delta_3 - \Delta_1}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

with c_{ijk} called the structure constants of the theory. They define the couplings between the fields, and so they define the particular theory in which we are working.

For up to three fields, the correlation functions are completely fixed by the conformal symmetry, up to a constant. With four fields or more, there are more degrees of freedom and the conformal symmetry does not fix them all. As a consequence, they are arbitrary functions of some cross ratios, which respect conformal symmetry.

In the limit $x_i \rightarrow x_j$, the expressions above are not well defined, as applying two different operators at the same point in space and time gives a divergent result. Under the hypothesis that the Hilbert space is complete, this can be rewritten as a sum of all the fields of the theory. This expansion has the form

$$\phi_1(x_1) \phi_2(x_2) \underset{x_1 \rightarrow x_2}{\sim} \sum_i \frac{c_{12i}}{r_{12}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 - \Delta_i}} \phi_i(x_1) \quad (15)$$

and is called the Operator Product Expansion (OPE). The OPE expansion is valid inside expectation values. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \phi_1(x_1) \phi_2(x_2) \phi_3(x_3) \rangle &= \frac{c_{123}}{r_{12}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 - \Delta_3} r_{13}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_3 - \Delta_2} r_{23}^{\Delta_2 + \Delta_3 - \Delta_1}} \underset{x_1 \rightarrow x_2}{\sim} \frac{c_{123}}{r_{12}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 - \Delta_3} r_{13}^{2\Delta_3}} \\ &\underset{x_1 \rightarrow x_2}{\sim} \sum_i \frac{c_{12i}}{r_{12}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 - \Delta_i}} \langle \phi_i(x_1) \phi_3(x_3) \rangle = \frac{c_{123}}{r_{12}^{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 - \Delta_3} r_{13}^{2\Delta_3}}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

As a result, the constants c_{12i} must be the same structure constants that appear in the three-point functions of ϕ_1, ϕ_2 , and ϕ_i .

The OPE is an asymptotic expansion, and usually the radius of convergence is zero, due to terms that are essential singularities of the type $e^{-a/r_{12}}$. Since CFTs are scale-invariant theories, there cannot be terms with a scaling dimension such as a . This means that the OPE has a finite radius of convergence, and this is one of the most important properties of CFTs, because on the one hand it reduces the number of parameters of the theory, and on the other it permits one to relate the fields and find constraints on the c_{ijk} .

In two dimensions, a field is defined as "primary" if it transforms as

$$\phi(z, \bar{z}) \xrightarrow{z \rightarrow f(z), \bar{z} \rightarrow \bar{f}(\bar{z})} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial z}\right)^{h_\phi} \left(\frac{\partial \bar{f}}{\partial \bar{z}}\right)^{\bar{h}_\phi} \phi(f(z), \bar{f}(\bar{z})) . \quad (17)$$

The OPE is valid for any field, but takes the special form of the above for both primary and quasi-primary scalar fields.

2.2.2 Stress-energy tensor

The stress-energy tensor is defined as the conserved current under conformal transformations.⁵ If S is the action of the system, then, under a conformal transformation, it must be $0 = \delta S =: (2\pi)^{d-1} \int d^d x \partial_\mu (T^{\mu\nu} \epsilon_\nu)$, since the energy cannot depend on the coordinate transformations. In particular, this means that $\partial_\mu (T^{\mu\nu} \epsilon_\nu) = 0$.

Since $T^{\mu\nu}$ is conserved under translations ($\partial_\mu T^{\mu\nu} = 0$), then $0 = \partial_\mu (T^{\mu\nu} \epsilon_\nu) = T^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \epsilon_\nu = T^{\mu\nu} (\partial_\mu \epsilon_\nu + \partial_\nu \epsilon_\mu) / 2 = d^{-1} (\partial \cdot \epsilon) T^{\mu\nu} \eta_{\mu\nu}$. As a result of conformal symmetry, the stress tensor is traceless, as well as symmetric. In two dimensions, T takes the form

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} T_{00} & T_{01} \\ T_{01} & -T_{00} \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

and its components can be rearranged into the sum of a purely holomorphic operator and a purely antiholomorphic one:

$$T(z) := \frac{1}{2}(T_{00} - iT_{01}) \quad \bar{T}(\bar{z}) := \frac{1}{2}(T_{00} + iT_{01}) \quad \partial_z \bar{T} = \bar{\partial}_z T = 0 . \quad (19)$$

The corresponding conserved charge, which implements the conformal transformations of the fields, is

$$Q = (2\pi i)^{-1} \oint (dz \epsilon(z) T(z) + d\bar{z} \bar{\epsilon}(\bar{z}) \bar{T}(\bar{z})) \quad (20)$$

$$\delta_{\epsilon\bar{\epsilon}} \phi(w, \bar{w}) = (2\pi i)^{-1} \oint ([dz \epsilon(z) T(z), \phi(w, \bar{w})] + [d\bar{z} \bar{\epsilon}(\bar{z}) \bar{T}(\bar{z}), \phi(w, \bar{w})]) .$$

⁵To be more precise, the conserved current is $T^{\mu\nu} \epsilon_\mu$, where $T^{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor and ϵ_μ is an infinitesimal conformal transformation.

Figure 2: Equal-radius integral paths of equation 21. The singularity at w is avoided above and below w based on the definition of the commutator.

Since the commutator is defined at equal radii, the integrals above have a singularity when $z = w$. To deal with this, we need to use the radial-ordering prescription. Let us study just the holomorphic part; the antiholomorphic part is analogous. The transformation of the field becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta_\epsilon \phi(w, \bar{w}) &= (2\pi i)^{-1} \oint dz [\epsilon(z)T(z), \phi(w, \bar{w})] = \\
&= (2\pi i)^{-1} \left\{ \oint_{|z|>|w|} dz \epsilon(z) R(T(z)\phi(w, \bar{w})) - \oint_{|z|<|w|} dz \epsilon(z) R(T(z)\phi(w, \bar{w})) \right\} = \\
&= (2\pi i)^{-1} \oint_w dz \epsilon(z) R(T(z)\phi(w, \bar{w})) .
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

On the other hand, the transformation rule for primary fields in 17 implies

$$\delta_\epsilon \phi(w, \bar{w}) = h_\phi \partial_w \epsilon(w) \phi(w, \bar{w}) + \epsilon(w) \partial_w \phi(w, \bar{w}) \tag{22}$$

where $f(z) = z + \epsilon(z)$. This implies the short-distance behavior (and so the OPE) of the stress tensor with a primary field

$$T(z)\phi(w, \bar{w}) = \left(\frac{h_\phi}{(z-w)^2} + \frac{\partial_w}{z-w} \right) \phi(w, \bar{w}) + \dots \quad \text{radially ordered} \tag{23}$$

and similarly for $\bar{T}(\bar{z})$. The expansion of the product of these fields has at most a double pole singularity. That holds for all primary fields.

Let us study how $T(z)$ itself changes under a conformal transformation. From dimensional considerations of the previous integrals, it must be that $h_T = \bar{h}_{\bar{T}} = 2$. From the Ward identities, $\langle T(z)T(w) \rangle \propto (z-w)^{-4}$. By further analysis, it can be found that the product of two stress tensors gives

$$T(z)T(w) = \frac{c/2}{(z-w)^4} + \frac{2}{(z-w)^2} T(w) + \frac{\partial_w}{z-w} T(w) \tag{24}$$

the stress tensor transforms as

$$T(z) \rightarrow (\partial f)^2 T(f(z)) + \frac{c}{12} \{f, z\} \quad \{f, z\} = \frac{\partial f \partial^3 f - 3(\partial^2 f)^2/2}{(\partial f)^2}, \quad (25)$$

where c is called the "central charge" of the theory and $\{f, z\}$ is the Schwarzian derivative of f . To have a lighter notation, we omit the subscript z when writing the derivatives. Since there is a fourth-order pole in $(z - w)$, $T(z)$ is not a primary field, but it is a quasi-primary field.

Since $T(z)$ (and $\bar{T}(\bar{z})$) are purely (anti)holomorphic, they can be expanded in a Laurent series, similarly to $\epsilon(z)$, of holomorphic operators L_n

$$T(z) = \sum_n L_n z^{-n-2} \quad L_n := \oint \frac{dz}{2\pi i} z^{n+1} T(z). \quad (26)$$

Using equation 24, the commutation relations are derived and are found to be as follows:

$$[L_n, L_m] = (n - m)L_{n+m} + \frac{c}{12} n(n^2 - 1)\delta_{n+m,0}, \quad (27)$$

which is the Virasoro algebra. Compared to the classical algebra, there is a term proportional to the central charge. The name "central charge," indeed, comes from the fact that the term proportional to $c \delta_{n+m,0}$ is the center of the Virasoro algebra, because it commutes with all the other elements. If the l_n operators encode the coordinate transformations, the L_n operators tell us how the fields change according to the previous ones.

Let us make a few comments on the constant c . The terms associated with it are anomaly terms because they "softly" break the conformal symmetry. Indeed, the extra term in the stress tensor transformation describes how the system reacts to macroscopic length changes [12] that affect the geometry of the theory. In particular, it reflects the reaction of the system to a change in the boundary conditions.

Consider the transformation from the plane to the cylinder. This map is $z \rightarrow z' = R \ln(z)$ for a cylinder of radius R . Then $T^{cyl}(z') = R^{-2}(z^2 T^{plane}(z) - c/24)$. The expectation value on the plane of a single operator insertion is zero due to the Ward identities, so that $\langle T^{plane}(z) \rangle = 0$. Then $\langle T^{cyl} \rangle \neq 0$, and in particular it depends both on the size of the cylinder and on the central charge $\langle T^{cyl} \rangle = -c/(24R^2)$. This can be interpreted as the Casimir energy for a system with periodic boundary conditions and finite size.

Another example of the role of c is that of a system that lives on a curved manifold, where the curvature introduces a macroscopic scale dependence. In this case, the stress tensor is not traceless anymore and the expectation value of the trace is proportional to both the central charge and the curvature.

Let us return to the primary fields. The fields obtained by the action of L_{-n} , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, on primary fields are called secondary fields. For every primary field, there are infinite secondary

Figure 3: The integral around an insertion at z can be rewritten as the sum of integrals around all the other insertions. This is a general property of integrals in \mathbb{C} .

fields associated with it, and they form its "conformal family".

The stress tensor is a secondary field that is derived from the identity. It is easy to see that

$$L_{-2}\mathbb{1} = L_{-2}\mathbb{1}(z) = \oint_z \frac{dw}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{w-z} T(w)\mathbb{1}(z) = T(z) \quad (28)$$

which also holds inside correlators.

It is possible to find the correlation functions of secondary fields by reconstructing the action of the operator L_{-n} on the corresponding primaries. Then the correlation function becomes a sum over integrals of T acting on the primaries around the insertions of these. Indeed, since there are no singularities placed at infinity, we can rewrite the original residue around z as the sum of residues around each z_i . The result is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle [L_{-k}\phi(z)]\phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n)\rangle &= \\ &= \left\langle \left[\oint_z \frac{dw}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{(w-z)^{k-1}} T(w)\phi(z) \right] \phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n) \right\rangle = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left\langle \phi(z) \left[\oint_{z_i} \frac{dw}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{(w-z)^{k-1}} T(w)\phi_i(z_i) \right] \phi_1\cdots\phi_{i-1}\phi_{i+1}\cdots\phi_n \right\rangle = \quad (29) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left[-\frac{(1-k)h_i}{(z_i-z)^k} - \frac{\partial_i}{(z_i-z)^{k-1}} \right] \langle \phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n)\rangle = \\ &:= \mathcal{L}_{-k}\langle \phi(z)\phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n)\rangle . \end{aligned}$$

This procedure is important in order to obtain constraints on the structure constants and bound them.

In particular, since T is a secondary field of the identity, the procedure above expresses the correlators including T in terms of correlators of the other insertions:

Figure 4: Representation of the conformal transformations to pass from the plane to the torus. The first step is to map the plane onto an infinite strip with the logarithm map. Then we take periodic boundary conditions in both directions.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle T(z)\phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n)\rangle &= \left\langle \left[\oint_z \frac{dw}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{w-z} T(w)\mathbb{1}(z) \right] \phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n) \right\rangle = \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_{-2}\langle\phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n)\rangle \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left[-\frac{h_i}{(z_i-z)^2} + \frac{\partial_i}{z_i-z} \right] \langle\phi_1(z_1)\phi_2(z_2)\cdots\phi_n(z_n)\rangle .
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

2.2.3 CFT on a torus

As shown previously, in two dimensions $T_{\mu\nu}$ decouples into a holomorphic and an antiholomorphic part, and so do the operators L_n and \bar{L}_n acting on the fields. Also, correlation functions are sums of conformal blocks, which are factorized into the product of one holomorphic and one antiholomorphic function. Therefore, the theory on the infinite plane decouples into a holomorphic and an antiholomorphic sector.

This is true as long as the theory is at a critical point, while continuously shifting it away from these points makes the left and right sectors couple. This implies that only certain combinations of holomorphic and antiholomorphic functions are physical. Another way to study these properties is to couple the sectors via a change in the geometry of the theory. This is obtained by considering a CFT living on a torus, which is equivalent to a plane with periodic boundary conditions in two directions [12].

We can first map the plane onto a cylinder, and then cut the cylinder and glue the two ends. Since the initial and final states of the theory are obtained in the time limits $t \rightarrow -\infty$ and $t \rightarrow +\infty$, in radial quantization these correspond to the points at $r \rightarrow 0$ and $r \rightarrow +\infty$. In the cylinder representation, if t' is the coordinate running along the non-compactified direction, the initial and final states are mapped to $t' \rightarrow \pm\infty$. With periodic boundary conditions on the torus, they are mapped onto the same circumference.

Let us consider a lattice of spacing a on the plane. A torus can be defined by taking two independent lattice vectors and identifying all the points which differ by an integer combination of these. The theory depends only on the ratio of these two vectors, called the "modular

parameter", which we will denote by τ . The fields must obey periodicity conditions in both directions, and the action and partition function must be invariant under periodic translations. Let us denote the two vectors on the plane as ω_1 and ω_2 . The operator that translates the system parallel to ω_2 is $\exp(-a(H \operatorname{Im}\omega_2 - iP \operatorname{Re}\omega_2)/|\omega_2|)$. On a cylinder of circumference L , we have $H = (2\pi/L)(L_0 + \bar{L}_0 - c/12)$ and $P = (2\pi i/L)(L_0 - \bar{L}_0)$, with $\omega_1 = L$ and $|\omega_2| = ma$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$ [12]. The term proportional to c in H comes from the transformation rule of the stress tensor from the plane to the cylinder. Indeed, the operators on the cylinder are not the same as on the plane, and their form can be found by writing them as integrals of T . As a consequence, $L_0^{cyl} = L_0 - c/24$ and similarly for \bar{L}_0^{cyl} .

The partition function on the torus is the trace of the finite translation operator e^{-iP} to the power of m , since it is applied m times and the initial and final states are the same. Recalling $\tau = \omega_2/\omega_1$ and $w_1 = L$,

$$Z(\tau) = \operatorname{Tr} e^{-\frac{2\pi}{w_1}[(L_0 + \bar{L}_0 - c/12)\operatorname{Im}(w_2) + (L_0 - \bar{L}_0)\operatorname{Re}(w_2)]} = \operatorname{Tr} e^{2\pi i[\tau(L_0 - c/24) - \bar{\tau}(\bar{L}_0 - c/24)]}. \quad (31)$$

We can define the parameters $q = e^{2\pi i\tau}$ and $\bar{q} = e^{-2\pi i\tau}$, and the partition function reads

$$Z(\tau) = \operatorname{Tr}(q^{L_0 - c/24} \bar{q}^{\bar{L}_0 - c/24}). \quad (32)$$

A similar transformation will be performed in section 4.4, where w_2 is taken purely imaginary and equal to $2\pi i$, and w_1 is again the length of the cylinder.

A few more words about CFTs defined on a torus. The partition function must be independent of the $SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$ transformations on $\omega_{1,2}$. It is the large subgroup of diffeomorphisms on the manifold, which leave the latter invariant but change the form of the metric. If we perform one of these transformations on the plane, τ changes accordingly:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \omega'_1 \\ \omega'_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \omega_1 \\ \omega_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \tau \rightarrow \tau' = \frac{a\tau + b}{c\tau + d} \quad ad - bc = 1, \quad a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (33)$$

Asking the partition function to be invariant under $SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$, which is also called the "modular group", leads to the Verlinde formula [12]. This formula relates the cross-ratios, the structure constants, and the form of the cross-ratio-dependent functions to the modular transformations, bounding the former as a consequence.

The motivations to study theories on a torus are various: for example, it describes a CFT with finite size at finite temperature, taking periodic boundary conditions. Later, we will use periodic boundary conditions because the calculations are easier there, and we will map our system onto cylinders and tori. The cylinder map comes from imposing periodic boundary conditions after a certain time-evolution, thus corresponding to a system at finite temperature - see 4.3. We will also take periodic boundary conditions in the other direction of the cylinder, so that it becomes a torus, to simplify our calculation in section 4.4.

Figure 5: Example of a one-dimensional defect (blue line) in a three-dimensional space-time. One space-like slice is shaded in blue, while the dashed lines show the distances between the operators.

In addition, theories on the torus give further constraints to crossing on the plane, and therefore new info on consistent CFTs.

2.3 Defect Conformal Field Theory

A conformal defect is an extended operator in the CFT, and can also be seen as a non-local modification of the geometry of the theory. It arises in many phenomena, of which the most intuitive examples are boundaries and interfaces [5].

A conformal defect of dimension p breaks the conformal symmetry group $SO(1, d + 1)$ into $SO(1, p + 1) \times SO(q)$, where $p + q = d$. The subspace of the defect is invariant under conformal transformations, now performed on its p dimensions, while there is a residual symmetry of rotations around the defect.

The defect can be excited and its excitations are encoded by defect operators, which live on the defect subspace. Let us label x^a as the coordinates parallel to the defect and x^i as the orthogonal ones. Then a bulk operator depends on both sets of coordinates $O(x^a, x^i)$, while a defect operator depends only on the first ones $\hat{O}(x^a)$. From now on, the defect operators will be denoted with a hat, along with their scaling dimensions.

The presence of a defect enlarges the theory by adding the new set of defect operators. Moreover, as with bulk operators, they can be fused and developed with a corresponding operator expansion, a defect OPE. To be more precise, we can distinguish two different cases:

- Two defect operators are being fused on the defect. Since the defect subspace is a CFT itself, defect operators will be expanded with an OPE similar to the bulk case, but with

just defect operators and new associated coefficients.

- A bulk operator is brought close to the defect. In this case $x^i \rightarrow 0$ and the bulk operator is indistinguishable from a defect excitation. Thus it can be rewritten as [5]

$$O(x^a, x^i) \underset{x^i \rightarrow 0}{\sim} b_{O\hat{O}_1} |x^i|^{\hat{\Delta}_1 - \Delta} \hat{O}_1(x^a) + \dots \quad (34)$$

where $b_{O\hat{O}_i}$ are new constants in the defect theory.

The bulk OPE is not affected by the presence of a defect, since it is a local expansion. The defect OPE holds in correlation functions just as the bulk OPE does. Due to the change in symmetry, the Ward identities will also take a different form. Let us first restrict our attention to the defect subspace. Since conformal invariance is required on the defect, the Ward identities of defect excitations are the same as in a CFT without a defect, only restricted to the coordinates x^a . For scalars, the first results are

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{O}(x^a) \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle \hat{O}_1(x_1^a) \hat{O}_2(x_2^a) \rangle &= \frac{1}{|x_1^a - x_2^a|^{2\hat{\Delta}}} \quad \text{iff } \hat{\Delta}_1 = \hat{\Delta}_2 = \hat{\Delta}. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Let us focus on bulk excitations. It is possible to distinguish two cases: when the bulk operator is coupled to defect excitations and when it is coupled to another bulk operator. The total conformal symmetry is broken, so the second case also takes a different form than a CFT without a defect.

The easiest scenario is when there is only a bulk operator. Now its position with respect to the defect becomes important, and the distance must appear in its expectation value ⁶. Therefore,

$$\langle O(x^a, x^i) \rangle = a_O |x^i|^{-\Delta}. \quad (36)$$

Note that $\langle O(x^a, x^i) \rangle = \langle O(x^a, x^i) \hat{\mathbb{1}} \rangle$, so $a_O = b_{O\hat{\mathbb{1}}}$. In fact, there is also an identity operator living on the subspace of the defect, which has a zero scaling dimension.

In the next sections, we derive the two-point functions of bulk-to-defect and bulk-to-bulk scalar operators. We will concentrate on scalars, because this is the case of interest for this work.

2.3.1 Bulk-to-defect two-point function

Let us consider a primary bulk operator $O_1(x_1)$ and a primary defect operator $\hat{O}_2(x_2)$, where $x = (x^a, x^i)$ with x^i being the coordinates orthogonal to the defect.

Due to invariance under rotations around the defect and translations along the axes parallel to

⁶Remember that the only symmetry preserved in the bulk is under rotations around the defect. Moreover, its distance from the defect determines the values of the defect OPE.

the defect, the two-point function must depend only on the distance between the two operators and the distance between the bulk operator and the defect. These are, respectively, $|x_1 - x_2|$ and $|x_1^i|$, and the correlation function is $g(|x_1 - x_2|, |x_1^i|)$.

Performing a dilation λ on the coordinates, the correlation function is constrained to be of the form $g(\lambda|x_1 - x_2|, \lambda|x_1^i|) = \lambda^{-\Delta - \hat{\Delta}} g(|x_1 - x_2|, |x_1^i|)$. This leads to

$$\langle O_1(x_1) \hat{O}_2(x_2) \rangle = \frac{b_{O_1 \hat{O}_2}}{|x_1 - x_2|^{b\Delta - a\hat{\Delta}} |x_1^i|^{-(b-1)\Delta + (a+1)\hat{\Delta}}} f\left(\frac{|x_1 - x_2|}{|x_1^i|}\right) \quad (37)$$

where a and b are two integers and f is an arbitrary function of the ratio between the two distances.

Another constraint comes from the requirement of invariance under inversion, which is a conformal transformation that preserves the defect. Defining $y = \frac{x}{|x|^2}$, the Jacobian of the transformation is $J = \left|\frac{\partial y}{\partial x}\right| = \frac{1}{|x|^4}$, and the constraint reads

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_1(x_1) \hat{O}_2(x_2) \rangle &= \frac{b_{O_1 \hat{O}_2}}{|x_1|^{2\Delta} |x_2|^{2\hat{\Delta}}} \langle O_1(y_1) \hat{O}_2(y_2) \rangle = \\ &= \frac{b_{O_1 \hat{O}_2}}{|x_1|^{2\Delta} |x_2|^{2\hat{\Delta}}} \left(\frac{|x_1||x_2|}{|x_1 - x_2|}\right)^{b\Delta - a\hat{\Delta}} \left(\frac{|x_1|^2}{|x_1^i|}\right)^{-(b-1)\Delta + (a+1)\hat{\Delta}} f\left(\frac{|x_1 - x_2| |x_1|}{|x_1^i| |x_2|}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

where $|x_1 - x_2| \rightarrow |x_1 - x_2|/(|x_1||x_2|)$. This implies that

$$\begin{cases} 2\Delta = b\Delta - a\hat{\Delta} + 2(a+1)\hat{\Delta} - 2(b-1)\Delta \\ 2\hat{\Delta} = b\Delta - a\hat{\Delta} \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

while the only option for f is to be a constant. Then,

$$\langle O_1(x_1) \hat{O}_2(x_2) \rangle = \frac{b_{O_1 \hat{O}_2}}{|x_1 - x_2|^{2\hat{\Delta}} |x_1^i|^{\Delta - \hat{\Delta}}} . \quad (40)$$

It should be noticed that, unlike the case without defects, here the two-point function is not zero even for operators with different scaling dimensions. This also remains true for the bulk-to-bulk correlation function.

This is the explicit calculation of the two-point function. Instead, we could obtain the same result by just considering the transformations we are allowed to use to fix the points of our correlator. Indeed, let us consider the CFT without a defect. The analytic form of the correlation functions is fixed up to three operators, because we can fix their positions completely by using conformal transformations. For example, one operator can be mapped to infinity by one inversion, another can be mapped to the origin using one translation, and the third can be mapped to a fixed point on the plane, let's say $(0, 1)$, with one dilation and one rotation (transformations that are not moving the other operators anymore). The three operators can

then always be brought into this configuration in a unique way. If the correlation function is known there, one can always do the inverse transformations and the correlation function cannot depend on an undetermined function of the coordinates. On the other hand, if we have four operators, then the fourth has been moved by the above transformations to fix the first three ones, but its position is not uniquely determined. We have also used all the degrees of freedom of the conformal group, so we don't have any transformation left to fix the fourth operator. As a consequence, the four-point function is not completely fixed by conformal symmetry and it has a dynamical factor that is an undetermined function of the coordinates. More precisely, this function depends on specific coordinate combinations, called "cross-ratios", which are invariant under conformal transformations. Since in the four-point function we can fix everything but the position of the fourth operator, the correlator depends on two variables, because we are in two dimensions and the position is defined by two coordinates, and so on two cross-ratios. In higher dimensions, we can still rotate the operator onto a precise plane, so the correlation function will still depend on two cross-ratios.

Let us consider the two-dimensional case, where the defect is a straight line lying on the imaginary axis of \mathbb{C} , and the insertions of one bulk operator and one defect operator. We could use one inversion to map $x_2 \rightarrow \infty$, and one translation along the defect axis and one dilation to map $x_1 \rightarrow (0, 1)$. With respect to the case without a defect, we cannot use rotations around the origin, because they do not preserve the defect. Since everything is fixed, we already know that there are no cross-ratios involved, and so f must be a constant. Then, taking the limit $x_1^i \rightarrow 0$ and using the defect OPE

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_1(x_1)\hat{O}_2(x_2) \rangle &\underset{x_1^i \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \frac{b_{O_1\hat{O}_2}}{|x_1^i|^{\Delta-\hat{\Delta}}} \langle \hat{O}_2(x_1)\hat{O}_2(x_2) \rangle + (\text{subleading terms}) = \\ &= \frac{b_{O_1\hat{O}_2}}{|x_1^i|^{\Delta-\hat{\Delta}}|x_1^a - x_2^a|^{2\hat{\Delta}}} + (\text{subleading terms}). \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Let us then perform an inversion on the bulk-to-defect correlator. If $x_2 = \epsilon \rightarrow 0$, so that the defect operator is placed at the origin ⁷, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_1(x_1)\hat{O}_2(\epsilon) \rangle &= x_1^{-2\Delta}\epsilon^{-2\hat{\Delta}} \left\langle O_1\left(\frac{x_1}{|x_1|^2}\right)\hat{O}_2\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}\right)\right\rangle \rightarrow \\ &\xrightarrow{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} x_1^{-2\Delta}\epsilon^{-2\hat{\Delta}} \frac{b_{O_1\hat{O}_2}}{|x_1^i/x_1^2|^{\Delta-\hat{\Delta}}\epsilon^{-2\hat{\Delta}}} = \\ &= \frac{b_{O_1\hat{O}_2}}{|x_1^i|^{\Delta-\hat{\Delta}}|x_1|^{2\hat{\Delta}}} \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

using the defect OPE of O_1 and the fact that in this limit $|x_1^a/x_1^2 - (1/\epsilon)| \sim \epsilon$. We can then generalize to any position of the defect operator, and get 40.

⁷We can always do that with a translation along the defect axis.

2.3.2 Bulk-to-bulk two-point function

The bulk-to-bulk two-point function of $O_1(x_1)$ and $O_2(x_2)$, similarly to before, will depend on the relative position of the two operators $|x_1 - x_2| = x_{12}$ and on their distances from the defect $|x_1^i|$ and $|x_2^i|$. Following the same reasoning as before, we can use one translation along the parallel axis and one dilation to fix x_{12} . Indeed, in the previous case we could use the inversion on the defect operator because it was not moving the defect, but we cannot do the same with a bulk operator. As a result, we cannot uniquely fix the positions of the operators, just their relative distance. By also performing rotations around the defect, we obtain two coordinate parameters that are not fixed, and so two independent cross-ratios must be involved. These can be chosen as

$$\frac{|x_{12}|^2}{|x_1^i||x_2^i|} \quad \frac{x_1^i \cdot x_2^i}{|x_1^i||x_2^i|} \quad (43)$$

where the second takes into account only the components perpendicular to the defect. For the kinematic term, the bulk-to-bulk correlator without a defect is non-zero only if it is between the same operators. Here we must generalize it, taking into account that the expectation value of a single bulk operator is non-vanishing. The result is [5]

$$\langle O_1(x_1)O_2(x_2) \rangle = \frac{b_{O_1 O_2}}{|x_1^i|^{\Delta_1}|x_2^i|^{\Delta_2}} f\left(\frac{x_1 \cdot x_2}{|x_1^i||x_2^i|}, \frac{x_1^i \cdot x_2^i}{|x_1^i||x_2^i|}\right). \quad (44)$$

In two dimensions with a one-dimensional defect, the cross-ratios reduce to a single independent one, which can be written as

$$\xi = \frac{z_{12}\bar{z}_{12}}{(z_2 + \bar{z}_2)(z_3 + \bar{z}_3)} \quad (45)$$

where $z = x + i\tau$ and the defect is placed along the imaginary axis.

3 Interfaces and energy transmission

A conformal interface is a conformal defect of codimension one. It can either split the same theory into two parts or divide two different theories, which may communicate through it. It is interesting to study the interactions across the interface, since they tell us information about the interface itself, but they also permit us to better understand the CFTs involved. Indeed, it is a way to probe correlations between operators on opposite sides, as they contain very interesting physics.

The first interaction we can think of is the energy transmission. This is a general quantity that can always be defined in any theory, and this makes it a basic tool to investigate a QFT. The goal of this chapter is to study the energy transmission in a two-dimensional set-up, where the interface lies on the time axis. This can be interpreted as an impurity on a line or a chain that evolves in time and does not move. First, some basic knowledge of interfaces is reviewed, and then the energy transmission and reflection coefficients are defined and studied.

3.1 Conformal interfaces

Let us take two different two-dimensional CFTs, one on the left and one on the right side of an interface, which we take as a straight line that lies on the time axis ($x = 0$). The interface, to be conformal, must satisfy

$$T_L(z = i\tau) - \bar{T}_L(\bar{z} = -i\tau) = T_R(z = i\tau) - \bar{T}_R(\bar{z} = -i\tau) \quad (46)$$

where T_{LR} (and \bar{T}_{LR}) are the holomorphic (and antiholomorphic) parts of the stress tensor of the corresponding CFT. This relation is called the "Cardy condition" or "gluing condition," and it is found by imposing the interface to be invariant under time translations and scale transformations [20][26]. The meaning of this relation is that the interface cannot absorb energy, so this is entirely reflected or transmitted across the interface. Thus, reflection and transmission coefficients must be defined such that they always sum to one. We will denote them as \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{T} , respectively. Later, we will further distinguish the coefficients by a subscript L, R based on which side of the interface is originally excited. In principle, the coefficients can depend on that choice, and indeed they will.

Interfaces are classified based on their topological properties and on their interactions with bulk operators. In particular, an interface is called topological if

$$T_L(z = i\tau) = T_R(z = i\tau), \quad \bar{T}_L(\bar{z} = -i\tau) = \bar{T}_R(\bar{z} = -i\tau). \quad (47)$$

This means that the stress tensor is continuous across the interface. Thus, the position of the interface is not relevant, and it can be freely deformed. Correlation functions will not depend on that. Moreover, the incident energy on the interface will be totally transmitted since the flux is independent of the interface. Then, for topological interfaces $\mathcal{T}_L = \mathcal{T}_R = 1$. The opposite case is when the interface is factorizing the two theories and the two CFTs are completely independent. This is realized by the condition

$$T_L(z = i\tau) = \bar{T}_L(\bar{z} = -i\tau), \quad T_R(z = i\tau) = \bar{T}_R(\bar{z} = -i\tau). \quad (48)$$

Since the two sides are not correlated, the incident energy must be totally reflected, and $\mathcal{T}_L = \mathcal{T}_R = 0$.

Other interfaces are not further classified.

3.2 Energy flux

Transmission and reflection coefficients are found by measuring how much energy passes or does not pass across the interface, given an initial amount of energy for a certain excitation. Let us first show how to measure the total energy without interfaces.

Since we are studying CFTs, all the excitations will be light-like, and the flux of energy will be equal to the flux of momentum. For a general operator acting on a CFT, there will be two excitations. One will be right-moving and thus holomorphic, and one left-moving and

Figure 6: Left: Penrose diagram of the CFT with the insertion of an operator O at $(t = 0, x = 0)$. O creates two bumps, one right-moving (red) and one left-moving (black). The process can be time-reversed, thus we have the bumps also for $t < 0$. \mathcal{E} and $\bar{\mathcal{E}}$ measure the energy reaching infinity of the right- and left-moving excitation. Right: In the presence of an interface, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_L$ receives contributions from the left excitation and from the reflection of the right excitation. The state created by O depends on the interface since in the past there has been a scattering process, which results in the left-moving "past excitation" of O . This is due to the time-reversal symmetry of the process.

antiholomorphic. This split is easy to take into account thanks to the holomorphic properties of the stress tensor, whose T^{00} component measures the flux of energy and splits according to

$$T^{00}(x, t) = -(2\pi)^{-1}(T(z) + \bar{T}(\bar{z})) \quad z = x + i\tau = x - t. \quad (49)$$

The total amount of energy reaching infinity towards the right and towards the left is computed, respectively, by

$$\mathcal{E} = -(2\pi)^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dz T(z), \quad \bar{\mathcal{E}} = -(2\pi)^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\bar{z} \bar{T}(\bar{z}). \quad (50)$$

For free massless excitations, generated by a quasi-primary operator O and described by a plane wave, we expect $\mathcal{E} = \bar{\mathcal{E}}$.⁸

In the presence of an interface, the propagation of energy is altered locally and it splits into a reflected and a transmitted part, which depend on the interface. If we excite the left CFT, then it will be the right-moving excitation that will hit the interface. Then, we want to measure the energy \mathcal{E} collected on the right to get the transmission coefficient, and $\bar{\mathcal{E}}$ on the

⁸The plane wave state created by $O(x, t)$ is $|O, p^\mu\rangle = \int d^2x e^{ip \cdot x} O(x) |0\rangle$. Then $\langle O, p^\mu | \mathcal{E} | O, p^\mu \rangle = \langle O, p^\mu | \bar{\mathcal{E}} | O, p^\mu \rangle = |p|/2$ by conserving the total momentum.

left for the reflected energy, which will be left-moving.

What is really non-trivial is the construction of the excited state, because it is influenced by the presence of the interface and by a non-translationally invariant vacuum.

Let us discuss this problem first.

3.3 Excited state

Let us create an excited state on the left CFT by acting with a local operator O_L at $t = 0$. The excitation splits into a right-moving and a left-moving bump, the first hitting the interface. However, since the energy density has power-law tails, even at $t = 0$ the state is affected by the interface. For our analysis, we want to isolate the scattering process, thus the state should be prepared very far away (ideally at infinite distance) from the interface.

Let us choose a wave function with a compact support of size l .

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |f(x)|^2 dx = 1, \quad |f(x)| = 0 \text{ if } |x| > l \quad (51)$$

Given $D > l$, we can create a one-parameter family of states [20]

$$|O_L, D\rangle = \int d^2x f(z)f(\bar{z} + D)O_L(z, \bar{z})|0\rangle_I. \quad (52)$$

Imposing time-reversal symmetry, as occurs in our theory, the state created by O_L depends on the interface not only due to the power-law tails of the energy density, but also due to a scattering process that occurred in the past - see figure 6. Two bumps in the past are perfectly entangled such that they create the left-moving bump, which merges into O_L , after hitting the interface.

Since we want our state to be completely independent of the interface, in order to isolate the energy transmission only due to the scattering process after O_L is inserted, we want to apply the operator not only far away in spatial position, but also in the far past, so that the past history can be neglected. This can be reached via $D \rightarrow \infty$ along the light-cone axis. In this way we obtain a state as if there is no defect, in fact [20]

$$\lim_{D \rightarrow \infty} \langle O_L, D | O_L, D \rangle_I = \langle O_L, D | O_L, D \rangle. \quad (53)$$

Moreover, this procedure isolates the red bump in figure 6, which is the one we are interested in.

3.4 Transmission and reflection coefficients

The transmission and reflection coefficients are defined as [20]

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_L &= \lim_{D \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle O_L, D | \mathcal{E}_R | O_L, D \rangle_I}{\langle O_L, D | \mathcal{E}_L | O_L, D \rangle} \\
\mathcal{R}_L &= \lim_{D \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle O_L, D | \bar{\mathcal{E}}_L | O_L, D \rangle_I - \langle O_L, D | \bar{\mathcal{E}}_L | O_L, D \rangle}{\langle O_L, D | \mathcal{E}_L | O_L, D \rangle} \\
\mathcal{T}_R &= \lim_{D \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle O_R, D | \bar{\mathcal{E}}_L | O_R, D \rangle_I}{\langle O_R, D | \bar{\mathcal{E}}_R | O_R, D \rangle} \\
\mathcal{R}_R &= \lim_{D \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle O_R, D | \mathcal{E}_R | O_R, D \rangle_I - \langle O_R, D | \mathcal{E}_R | O_R, D \rangle}{\langle O_R, D | \bar{\mathcal{E}}_R | O_R, D \rangle}.
\end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

It can be shown that these definitions satisfy:

- $\mathcal{T} + \mathcal{R} = 1$;
- $\mathcal{T}_L = \mathcal{T}_R = 1$ for topological interfaces;
- $\mathcal{T}_L = \mathcal{T}_R = 0$ for factorizing interfaces;

using the action of T on the quasi-primary operators $O_{L,R}(z, \bar{z})$. It can be shown that these expectation values can be rewritten as integrals over the three-point functions $\langle O_{L/R}(z_1, \bar{z}_1) T_{L,R}(z) O_{L/R}(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \rangle_{(I)}$ and with $\bar{T}_{L,R}(\bar{z})$.

These coefficients are complicated objects for general states, but their calculation is much easier if we consider a holomorphic operator $O_{L/R}(z)$.

3.4.1 Holomorphic state

Let us consider the state created on the left CFT by a quasi-primary holomorphic operator $O_L(z)$. In general, $O_L(z)$ is a sum of operators $O_L(z) = \sum_i O_L^i(z)$ with scaling dimensions $(h_i, 0)$. Then the only excitation propagating is the right-moving one, and the state does not depend on the distance from the interface anymore - see figure 6. The consequence is that we do not need to consider the limit $D \rightarrow \infty$ nor the position of O_L at all, because the black bump is automatically dropped. The coefficients can now be found as the ratio of the correlators, not integrated anymore. Therefore the transmission coefficient is determined by

$$\langle O_L^1(z_1) T_{L,R}(z) O_L^2(z_2) \rangle = \frac{c_{12T_{L,R}}}{(z_1 - z_2)^{h_1+h_2-2} (z_1 - z)^{h_1-h_2+2} (z_2 - z)^{h_2-h_1+2}}. \tag{55}$$

We will compute this expression again below, using the so-called "method of images". We will show that the two agree, and justify the use of this method for more complicated point functions.

Even in the presence of an interface, the three-point function of holomorphic operators is fixed up to a coefficient and there are no cross-ratios involved. Indeed, since there is no

dependence on the \bar{z} 's, there is no dependence on the distance from the interface, and so the correlator has the same form as a three-point function without an interface.

We can then use the fusion OPE of $O_L^1 \times O_L^2$ to constrain $c_{12T_{L,R}}$. Let us assume that the only operator of scaling dimension $(2, 0)$ appearing in the OPE is T_L . Then the transmission coefficient depends only on the two-point functions $\langle T_L(z_1)T_R(z) \rangle_I$ and $\langle T_L(z_1)T_L(z) \rangle_I = \langle T_L(z_1)T_L(z) \rangle$. Let us define the new coefficient c_{LR} as [20][26]

$$\langle T_L(z_1)T_R(z) \rangle_I = \frac{c_{LR}/2}{(z_1 - z)^4}, \quad (56)$$

which is a piece of the CFT data. Then

$$\mathcal{T}_L = \frac{c_{LR}}{c_L} \quad (57)$$

where c_L is the central charge of the left CFT. Similarly, $\mathcal{T}_R = c_{LR}/c_R$.

The reflection coefficient is straightforward.

The constant c_{LR} is the one that governs the exchange of energy. All the information about the interaction between the CFTs across the interface is encoded there. It does not have a general value, but it strongly depends on the interface and on the CFTs. It cannot be derived and it is a piece of CFT data.

The transmission coefficient we have derived does not depend on the state, but only on the CFTs and on the type of interface. This holds for all the states we can construct, acting with any operator $O_{L/R}(z, \bar{z})$ [20].

Note that it must be $c_{LR} \leq \min(c_L, c_R)$ for consistency.

3.5 Method of images

We describe here a useful method to compute the conformal blocks of correlation functions in a defect theory. It was first developed for boundary CFTs, but it can be extended to this context. [21]

We apply this method to calculate the correlator in 55 as an example of its validity. We will use it in section 5 for more difficult correlation functions.

The image method consists of mirroring the operators with respect to the defect. In the original position, the original operator is placed but with the antiholomorphic scaling dimension set to zero, while its image is the original operator but with the holomorphic scaling dimension set to zero. We then evaluate the conformal blocks of the correlation functions of all the operators and their images as if there were no defect. Defect operators are not changed or mirrored.

The conformal blocks in these two configurations are the same because they satisfy the same conformal symmetry and the same relations between the coordinates. If there is more than one conformal block, these can be combined in different ways in the two configurations. We then only get the cross-ratio dependence, but not the form of the functions nor the dynamical

Figure 7: Image method. Procedure of mirroring the operators with respect to the defect.

factors. If there is just one conformal block, then there is no ambiguity and the two configurations are proportional to each other. The correlation function is then known completely. This method is useful to obtain the dynamic dependence of the correlators and to know how many cross-ratios and how many conformal blocks are involved, as calculations without defects are easier in general.

Let us discuss the previous case.

Consider the excitation generated by the insertion of the stress tensor on the left CFT, which is a holomorphic operator that is always present in every theory. We therefore consider the initial and final states $\langle T_L |$ and $| T_L \rangle$, and so the correlation functions we need to evaluate are $\langle T_L(z_1) T_R(z) T_L(z_2) \rangle_I$ and $\langle T_L(z_1) T_L(z) T_L(z_2) \rangle_I$. The second is the three-point function of holomorphic operators on the same side with respect to the interface, which means it does not depend on the interface ⁹

$$\langle T_L(z_1) T_L(z) T_L(z_2) \rangle_I = \langle T_L(z_1) T_L(z) T_L(z_2) \rangle .$$

We can then consider the action of one T_L on the other insertions, and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle T_L(z_1) T_L(z) T_L(z_2) \rangle &= \left\{ \frac{2}{(z_1 - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial_1}{z_1 - z_2} + \frac{2}{(z - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial}{z - z_2} \right\} \langle T_L(z_1) T_L(z) \rangle + \\ &\quad + \frac{c_L/2}{(z_1 - z_2)^4} \langle T_L(z) \rangle + \frac{c_L/2}{(z - z_2)^4} \langle T_L(z_1) \rangle = \\ &= \left\{ \frac{2}{(z_1 - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial_1}{z_1 - z_2} + \frac{2}{(z - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial}{z - z_2} \right\} \frac{c_L/2}{(z_1 - z)^4} = \\ &= c_L \frac{(z - z_2)^2 (3z_1 - z - 2z_2) + z_{12}^2 (z_1 - 3z + 2z_2)}{(z_1 - z)^4 z_{12}^2 (z - z_2)^2 (z_1 - z)} \end{aligned} \tag{58}$$

⁹This is because they are holomorphic operators. In particular, they do not depend on the antiholomorphic coordinate, and so on the distance from the defect - see section 5.

where $\partial = \partial/\partial z$ and $\partial_1 = \partial/\partial z_1$, $z_{12} = (z_1 - z_2)$ and we used the fact that the expectation value of a single insertion is zero.

Let us now consider $\langle T_L(z_1)T_R(z)T_L(z_2) \rangle_I$ and let us map it to the mirrored configuration. Since T_L is holomorphic, it remains itself while its image is an operator with scaling dimensions $(h = 0, \bar{h} = 0)$, that is, the identity. Thus, we get $\langle T_L(z_1)T_R(z)T_L(z_2)\mathbb{1}(\bar{z}_1)\mathbb{1}(\bar{z}_2) \rangle = \langle T_L(z_1)T_R(z)T_L(z_2) \rangle$. Again, this three-point function can be rewritten as differential operators applied to a two-point function:

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle T_L(z_1)T_R(z)T_L(z_2) \rangle &= \left\{ \frac{2}{(z_1 - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial_1}{z_1 - z_2} + \frac{2}{(z - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial}{z - z_2} \right\} \langle T_L(z_1)T_R(z) \rangle + \\
&\quad + \frac{c_L/2}{(z_1 - z_2)^4} \langle T_R(z) \rangle + \frac{c_{LR}/2}{(z - z_2)^4} \langle T_L(z_1) \rangle = \\
&= \left\{ \frac{2}{(z_1 - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial_1}{z_1 - z_2} + \frac{2}{(z - z_2)^2} - \frac{\partial}{z - z_2} \right\} \frac{c_{LR}/2}{(z_1 - z)^4} = \\
&= c_{LR} \frac{(z - z_2)^2(3z_1 - z - 2z_2) + z_{12}^2(z_1 - 3z + 2z_2)}{(z_1 - z)^4 z_{12}^2 (z - z_2)^2 (z_1 - z)}.
\end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

We easily obtain $\mathcal{T}_L = c_{LR}/c_L$.

4 Entanglement Entropy

In this section, we first briefly review some basic facts about entanglement and entanglement entropy in quantum mechanics. Then we describe what happens when one tries to extend these concepts to quantum field theory. Indeed, problems arise when considering a continuum space, since the definition of subsystems is delicate, and so is the evaluation of the density operator. We show how to deal with these problems, and introduce the Rényi entropies and the twist field formalism. We evaluate the Rényi entropies and the entanglement entropy in two-dimensional CFTs with and without a conformal interface. We finally introduce a new approach to evaluate the entanglement entropy in interface CFTs, by defining a new operator, the "defect twist operator", and calculating its scaling dimension.

4.1 Entanglement and density matrix in quantum systems

In quantum mechanics, the expectation value of an observable A is given by $\langle \hat{A} \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{A} | \psi \rangle$, where $|\psi\rangle$ is the state of the system. Equivalently, one can define the "density operator" ρ ,

$$\rho := |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| \quad \rho_{ij} = \langle e_i | \psi \rangle \langle \psi | e_j \rangle \tag{60}$$

where $\{|e_i\rangle\}$ is a basis of the Hilbert space and $|\psi\rangle$ is a pure state. We omit the hat on ρ for a lighter notation. The expectation value of \hat{A} can be written as

$$\langle \hat{A} \rangle = \text{Tr}(\rho \hat{A}) . \quad (61)$$

For pure states, the density matrix has the following properties:

$$\rho^2 = \rho \quad \rho^\dagger = \rho \quad \text{Tr}\rho = 1 . \quad (62)$$

For mixed states, that is, a mixture of pure states, it is still possible to define a density matrix, generalized as

$$\rho := \sum_k p_k |\psi_k\rangle \langle \psi_k| \quad \rho_{ij} := \sum_k p_k \langle e_i | \psi_k \rangle \langle \psi_k | e_j \rangle \quad (63)$$

where $\sum_k p_k^2 = 1$, $0 \leq p_k \leq 1$. All the above properties remain valid, except for the idempotence property, because now $\rho^2 \neq \rho$ and therefore $\text{Tr}\rho^2 < 1$.

Given an entangled state $|\Psi\rangle$ in a bipartite system with total Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B$, we can define the reduced density matrix of the subsystem A as

$$\rho_A = \text{Tr}_B \rho \quad (64)$$

where we trace out the degrees of freedom of the subsystem B from the total density matrix. If the state $|\Psi\rangle$ cannot be written as the product of a state in \mathcal{H}_A and a state in \mathcal{H}_B , then the two subsystems are entangled. This means that the two subsystems are correlated and a measurement on A influences the state of B . The "entanglement entropy" of the subsystem A is the von Neumann entropy of its reduced density matrix

$$S_A := -\text{Tr}(\rho_A \ln \rho_A) . \quad (65)$$

For pure states, S of the total system is zero and $S_A = S_B$, since the uncertainty of the subsystems is only due to the entanglement. Indeed, S measures the lack of information about the systems.¹⁰ If the total state is not pure, then there is uncertainty coming from the measurement, which can give different results, and the reduced entanglement entropy contains both the lack of information about the measurement and the entanglement. Thus, in general $S_A \neq S_B$.

The definition of the entanglement entropy satisfies unitarity and additivity, as an entropy should,

$$S(U\rho U^\dagger) = S(\rho) , \quad S(\rho \otimes \sigma) = S(\rho) + S(\sigma) ,$$

and if we normalize it such that $S(\mathbb{1}/2) = \ln 2$, then we will consider $S(\rho) = -\text{Tr}(\rho \ln \rho) / \text{Tr}(\rho)$.

¹⁰If the total state is pure, there is no uncertainty about $|\psi\rangle$, but there is uncertainty in the outcome of a measurement restricted to A , without access to B . Even knowing all the matrix elements of ρ_A , there is no basis of measurements that gives us full knowledge of the outcome without doing the experiment. Instead, if we consider the density matrix of the pure state $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ in the basis $\{|\psi\rangle, (\text{orthog. complete})\}$, we know all the outcomes.

The entanglement entropy satisfies a series of interesting inequalities. An important one that we will use later involves a quantity that is called "relative entropy" and is defined as

$$S(\rho||\sigma) := \text{Tr}(\rho \ln \rho) - \text{Tr}(\rho \ln \sigma) . \quad (66)$$

It satisfies

$$S(\rho||\sigma) \geq 0 , \quad S(\rho||\sigma) = 0 \quad \text{iff} \quad \rho = \sigma . \quad (67)$$

It is a measure of how much a system with density matrix ρ differs from the case in which it is described by the density matrix σ . Classically, it is the error made by predictions which take into account σ to describe the system, when it is actually described by ρ .

4.1.1 EPR pair

The simplest example of a bipartite system is composed of two qubits, where each of them can be in the state up ($|\uparrow\rangle$) or down ($|\downarrow\rangle$). [16, 27] Let \mathcal{H}_A be the Hilbert space of the first qubit, and \mathcal{H}_B the Hilbert space of the second qubit. The total Hilbert space is $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B$. The EPR (Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen) pair is the above system when it is in the state

$$|\text{EPR}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\downarrow\rangle) \quad (68)$$

and it holds that

$$\exists |A\rangle \in \mathcal{H}_A, \quad |B\rangle \in \mathcal{H}_B \quad \text{such that} \quad |\text{EPR}\rangle = |A\rangle|B\rangle . \quad (69)$$

The values of the third component of the spin for the two systems are completely correlated. The reduced density matrix for the subsystem A is

$$\rho_A = \text{Tr}_B \rho = \text{Tr}_B |\text{EPR}\rangle\langle\text{EPR}| = \frac{1}{2}(|\uparrow\rangle\langle\uparrow| + |\downarrow\rangle\langle\downarrow|) . \quad (70)$$

ρ_A cannot be written as the density matrix of a pure state $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$, which means that the state is mixed. Indeed,

$$(\rho_A)_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Tr} \rho_A^2 < 1 . \quad (71)$$

As a consequence, there is no experiment whose outcome is certain if we do not have access to B . The associated entanglement entropy is

$$S_A(\rho_A) = -\text{Tr}(\rho_A \ln \rho_A) = \ln 2 = S_B(\rho_B) , \quad (72)$$

that is, the information carried by one qubit in a maximally entangled bipartite system is one bit.

Figure 8: UV cut-off and discretization of the theory.

4.2 Entanglement in Quantum Field Theory

Let us discuss what happens in quantum field theory. The main problem in the definition of the entanglement entropy is that the space is now continuous, and dividing the system into two parts is an ill-defined operation. Suppose that we want to divide the space into two subsystems A and B . There are UV modes at any arbitrary scale, and thus they also exist across the surface ∂A that divides A from B . Then, UV divergences arise on the boundary between the two subsystems, and it is impossible to split the total Hilbert space. We therefore need to define a UV cut-off ϵ . In this way, the Hilbert space can now be split, and it is possible to define S_A , with the same properties as in quantum mechanics.

It is possible to find a general structure for the divergent parts of S_A . Since we are dealing with UV divergences, which are local, the divergent terms will come from a local integral over the boundary ∂A of some functional F of the curvature K_{ab} and the induced metric h_{ab} [16]¹¹

$$S_A^{div} \sim \int_{\partial A} d^{d-2}x \sqrt{h} F[K_{ab}, h_{ab}]. \quad (73)$$

We can expand it in powers of K_{ab} . The curvature goes as $K_{ab} \sim 1/L_A$, where L_A is the size of A . Since in a pure state $S_A = S_B$, and the curvature flips sign when evaluated on the other side of the surface, there must be only even powers of K_{ab} , and therefore of L_A . This means that, by dimensional analysis of the above integral,

$$S_A^{div} \sim a_{d-2} L_A^{d-2} + a_{d-4} L_A^{d-4} + \dots \quad (74)$$

Note that the leading term is proportional to the area of the region A . This must be the case since the UV modes are proportional to that area.

For a scale-invariant theory, such as our case of interest, the only scales involved must be L_A and ϵ , which implies $a_{d-2} \sim \epsilon^{2-d}$, $a_{d-4} \sim \epsilon^{4-d}$ and so on, since the entanglement entropy is dimensionless. Thus,

¹¹To be precise, this is true when the cut-off is invariant under diffeomorphisms.

$$\begin{cases} S_A^{odd} \sim b_{d-2} \left(\frac{L_A}{\epsilon}\right)^{d-2} + b_{d-4} \left(\frac{L_A}{\epsilon}\right)^{d-4} + \dots + b_1 \frac{L_A}{\epsilon} + (-1)^{(d-1)/2} \tilde{S} + O(\epsilon) \\ S_A^{even} \sim b_{d-2} \left(\frac{L_A}{\epsilon}\right)^{d-2} + b_{d-4} \left(\frac{L_A}{\epsilon}\right)^{d-4} + \dots + b_2 \left(\frac{L_A}{\epsilon}\right)^2 + \\ \quad + (-1)^{(d-2)/2} \tilde{S} \ln \frac{L_A}{\epsilon} + \text{const} + O(\epsilon) \end{cases} \quad (75)$$

where the sign (-1) in front of \tilde{S} is a convention.

The quantity \tilde{S} does not depend on the regulator or on the size of the subsystem, so it is a universal contribution.¹² \tilde{S} is also called the "renormalized entanglement entropy".

4.3 Rényi entropies

Even though it is possible to formally define the entanglement entropy for quantum field theories, the effective calculation is difficult and rarely achieved. In fact, the entanglement entropy depends on the logarithm of the density operator. This quantity is easy to calculate whenever the density matrix is diagonalized, an operation that is very hard in QFT. It is convenient then to define new quantities, called the Rényi entropies

$$S_A^{(n)}(\rho) = \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \frac{\text{Tr} \rho_A^n}{(\text{Tr} \rho_A)^n}. \quad (76)$$

These quantities are formally obtained by a generalization of the arithmetic mean rule that the entanglement entropy obeys. They also correspond to physical observables, which can be measured in condensed matter systems.

The Rényi entropies are well defined in the sense that the sum over powers of eigenvalues of ρ which defines $S_A^{(n)}$ is convergent. Indeed, $\text{Tr} \rho_A$ is convergent since its eigenvalues lie in the interval $[0, 1]$ and they sum to one. Raising it to the n -th power makes it absolutely convergent and analytic for $\text{Re } n > 1$. It still has UV divergences, regularized by the cut-off ϵ .

The entanglement entropy is recovered via the limit

$$S_A = \lim_{n \rightarrow 1} S_A^{(n)}. \quad (77)$$

For diagonal density matrices, this exponentiation is straightforward for any real (or complex) n . To see it, let us take a diagonal density matrix with eigenvalues $\lambda_i \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_i \lambda_i = 1$. Then $\text{Tr} \rho_A^n = \sum_i \lambda_i^n$ and it is absolutely convergent and analytic. The derivative is therefore $\sum_i \lambda_i^n \ln \lambda_i \rightarrow \sum_i \lambda_i \ln \lambda_i$ for $n \rightarrow 1$, which is precisely minus the entanglement entropy for a system described by a diagonal density matrix.

If ρ is not diagonal, $\text{Tr} \rho_A^n$ is well-defined only for integer n , but the analytic continuation is harder. It becomes an issue when trying to recover the entanglement entropy via the limiting

¹²It still depends on the theory and on the state, though.

procedure, which implies a real value of n . This problem has already been addressed [7] and we will ignore it here, assuming that the continuation is unique and well defined. Hence, we will compute $\text{Tr}\rho_A^n$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and analytically continue it to complex values. This also implies

$$S_A = -\lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \partial_n \text{Tr}\rho_A^n \quad (78)$$

when S_A is finite [7]. The calculation of $\text{Tr}\rho_A^n$ corresponds to the evaluation of a partition function defined on an n -sheeted Riemann surface, obtained by replicating the theory on the plane n times. Although the surface can be rather complicated, the calculation of the partition function there is achievable through QFT tools. This procedure usually goes under the name of the "replica trick".

Let us see how to construct and deal with the new replicated theory. After defining the UV cut-off, the QFT is defined on a lattice of spacing unit ϵ and the sites are positioned in cells denoted by x . Let us define $\{\hat{\phi}(x)\}$ as a complete set of commuting variables with corresponding eigenvalues $\{\phi_x\}$ and eigenvectors $|\{\phi_x\}\rangle$. One basis for the theory is then $\{|\prod_x \{\phi_x\}\rangle\}$. The elements of the density matrix are

$$\rho(\{\phi_x\}|\{\phi'_{x'}\}) = Z^{-1} \int_{0 \leq \tau \leq \tau_1} [\mathcal{D}\phi(y, \tau)] \prod_{x'} \delta(\phi(y, 0) - \phi'_{x'}) \prod_x \delta(\phi(y, \tau_1) - \phi_x) e^{-S_E} \quad (79)$$

where S_E is the Euclidean action of the system.¹³

The trace of ρ is found by imposing $\phi_x = \phi'_{x'}$ and integrating over all x , which corresponds to implementing periodic boundary conditions in the time direction. The factor Z ensures the correct normalization $\text{Tr}\rho = 1$.

Let us consider a spatial interval A . The discussion can be easily generalized to the case when A consists of many disjoint intervals. Taking the reduced density matrix ρ_A corresponds to tracing out ρ only over those sites that are not in A [7]. This is equivalent to leaving an open cut over the sites in A . It can be seen as a cylinder that has not been sewn along A . We can then use the replica trick and define a new surface obtained by gluing together n copies of the CFT, such that $\phi_j(x, \tau_1^-) = \phi_{j+1}(x, 0^+)$, $1 \leq j \leq n$ and $\phi_n(x, \tau_1^-) = \phi_1(x, 0^+)$. These copies are glued along the cut A . ρ_A^n is then the density matrix on the new Riemann surface, and $\text{Tr}\rho_A^n$ is the trace over \bar{A} . If Z_n is the partition function on this surface,

$$\text{Tr}\rho_A^n = \frac{Z_n}{Z_1^n} \quad (80)$$

¹³In the formula we are assuming the system to evolve from the Euclidean time $\tau = 0$ to $\tau = \tau_1$, with $S_E = \int_0^{\tau_1} d\tau \mathcal{L}_E$. In later sections, we will consider theories at zero temperature, and the time interval goes from $\tau \rightarrow -\infty$ to $\tau \rightarrow +\infty$.

Figure 9: Riemann surface of the replicated theory with $n = 3$.

where Z_1 is the partition function on one sheet and ensures the correct normalization.

4.3.1 Twist fields

It can be shown that the effective position of the cut A is not relevant for the evaluation of the entanglement entropy, while its endpoints (or its boundary in higher dimensions) are. The information is then encoded along the entangling surface by the insertion of a "twist operator" Φ_n .

Note that this operator has codimension two. In higher dimensions, it is an extended operator and is treated as a defect. In two dimensions, the entangling surface is a segment and its boundary consists of two points. We therefore have two local twist operators, denoted Φ_n and Φ_{-n} , inserted at those two endpoints.

A rotation of one operator inserted on the i -th sheet around Φ_n will bring it to the $(i + 1)$ -th sheet, while it goes to the $(i - 1)$ -th sheet if it rotates around Φ_{-n} .

Twist fields can be interpreted as the fields that realize a new symmetry, which arises on the n -sheeted surface. In fact, the new theory is invariant under a global shift of the sheets.

The partition function on the Riemann surface becomes the correlation function of these fields, up to a constant

$$Z_n \propto \langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle \quad (81)$$

with u and v being the endpoints of A .

In general, the expectation value of an operator $O_i(w)$ inserted on the i -th sheet will be

$$\langle O_i(w) \rangle_n = \frac{\langle O_i(w) \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle}{\langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle}. \quad (82)$$

The evaluation of the partition function is now easier, because it is reduced to a correlation function. It remains to understand the nature of the twist fields in order to find this correlator.

Figure 10: The uniformizing map brings the Riemann surface to a single complex plane. In the figure, the case $n = 3$ is represented.

To do so, we consider the insertion of the total stress tensor (that is, a stress tensor on each sheet) and infer information about the twist operators from its expectation value. We then evaluate the entanglement entropy for a finite interval.

4.3.2 Twist fields scaling dimension and Entanglement entropy for a single interval

Let us consider the map that first brings the endpoints of A to $u \rightarrow 0$ and $v \rightarrow \infty$, and secondly maps the entire surface onto one complex plane. This map is called the "uniformizing map", and it reads

$$w \rightarrow \zeta = \frac{w - u}{w - v} \rightarrow z = \zeta^{1/n} = \left(\frac{w - u}{w - v} \right)^{1/n} . \quad (83)$$

The single insertion of a stress tensor transforms according to

$$T(w) = \left(\frac{dz}{dw} \right)^2 T(z) + \frac{c}{12} \{z, w\} . \quad (84)$$

The expectation value of the above expression, if we consider it to be equal to zero in the vacuum on the infinite plane, is

$$\langle T(w) \rangle = \frac{c}{12} \{z, w\} = \frac{c}{24} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2} \right) \frac{(v - u)^2}{(w - u)^2 (w - v)^2} \quad (85)$$

which is equal to $\langle T(w) \rangle = \langle T^{(i)}(w) \rangle = \langle T^{(i)}(w) \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle / \langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle$.¹⁴ The total stress tensor on the Riemann surface is obtained by n insertions of $T^{(i)}(w)$, so its expectation value is n times the previous one:

$$\langle \mathcal{T}(w) \rangle = \frac{\langle \mathcal{T}(w) \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle}{\langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle} = \frac{c}{24} \left(n - \frac{1}{n} \right) \frac{(v - u)^2}{(w - u)^2 (w - v)^2} \quad (86)$$

¹⁴This is by the definition of the one-point function in the presence of open cuts, described by these fields.

where $\mathcal{T}(w) = \sum_i \mathbb{1}^{\otimes(i-1)} \otimes T^{(i) \otimes \mathbb{1}^{\otimes(n-i)}}(w)$. Let Φ_n and Φ_{-n} be two primary scalar fields with scaling dimension $\Delta_n = h_n + \bar{h}_n = 2h_n$, inserted respectively at positions u and v . Their two-point function is given by

$$\langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle = \frac{1}{(u-v)^{2h_n} (u-v)^{2\bar{h}_n}} , \quad (87)$$

and the insertion of the stress tensor leads to the Ward identity

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{T}(w) \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle &= \\ &= \left(\frac{h_n}{(w-u)^2} + \frac{h_n}{(w-v)^2} + \frac{\partial_u}{w-u} + \frac{\partial_v}{w-v} \right) \langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (88)$$

since they are primaries. Using 87 we obtain

$$\langle \mathcal{T}(w) \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle = \frac{h_n}{(w-u)^2 (w-v)^2 (u-v)^{2h_n-2} (\bar{u}-\bar{v})^{2\bar{h}_n}} \quad (89)$$

and so the expectation value of the stress tensor is

$$\langle \mathcal{T}(w) \rangle = \frac{\langle \mathcal{T}(w) \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle}{\langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle} = \frac{h_n (u-v)^2}{(w-u)^2 (w-v)^2} . \quad (90)$$

By comparison, it is easy to obtain

$$h_n = \frac{c}{24} \left(n - \frac{1}{n} \right) \implies \Delta_n = \frac{c}{12} \left(n - \frac{1}{n} \right) . \quad (91)$$

Recalling that

$$\text{Tr}(\rho_A^n) \propto \langle \Phi_n(u) \Phi_{-n}(v) \rangle \quad (92)$$

we are now able to find the entanglement entropy for a finite interval. If we define $L = |u-v|$ and introduce a UV cut-off to obtain a dimensionless result, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(\rho_A^n) &= \tilde{c}'_n \left(\frac{L}{\epsilon} \right)^{-2\Delta_n} = \tilde{c}'_n \left(\frac{L}{\epsilon} \right)^{-\frac{c}{6} \frac{n^2-1}{n}} \\ S_A^{(n)} &= \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \frac{\text{Tr}(\rho_A^n)}{(\text{Tr} \rho_A)^n} = \tilde{c}_n + \frac{c}{6} \frac{n+1}{n} \ln \frac{L}{\epsilon} \end{aligned} \quad (93)$$

where \tilde{c}_n is a constant that in general depends on the theory and the number of copies. It also changes when changing the cut-off, so it is not universal. Even so, it does not add interesting physics in the absence of boundaries. [29] The entanglement entropy of the system is found via the limit as $n \rightarrow 1$

$$S_A = - \lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \partial_n \text{Tr}(\rho_A^n) = c_1 + \tilde{c}_1 \frac{c}{3} \ln \left(\frac{L}{\epsilon} \right) \quad (94)$$

where $\lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \partial_n \tilde{c}_n = c_1$. To fix \tilde{c}_1 , it has to be considered that $\lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \frac{\text{Tr}(\rho_A^n)}{\text{Tr}(\rho_A)^n} = 1$, so that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \frac{\tilde{c}_n \left(\frac{L}{\epsilon} \right)^{-\frac{c}{6} \frac{n^2-1}{n}}}{1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \frac{\tilde{c}_n}{1} = 1 \quad (95)$$

which means $\tilde{c}_1 = 1$. The entanglement entropy is therefore

$$S_A = c_1 + \frac{c}{3} \ln \left(\frac{L}{\epsilon} \right) . \quad (96)$$

Note that the leading term is proportional to the logarithm of L/ϵ , which diverges for $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. Compared to equation 75, the renormalized entropy is $c/3$, where c is the central charge of the theory. This is a universal result for two-dimensional CFTs.

4.4 Interface insertion

In this section we describe what happens when an interface is inserted. We first review the general approach and define the effective central charge. We then propose a new approach, by defining a defect OPE for the twist fields and relating the scaling dimension of the defect twist operator to the central charge.

4.4.1 Effective central charge

Let the two-dimensional space be composed of two different CFTs, namely CFT_L and CFT_R , which lie respectively in the $x < 0$ and $x > 0$ half-planes. Their junction lies on the time axis and will be indicated as the interface operator I_{LR} . The region A for which we want to evaluate the Rényi entropy is the real positive axis $x > 0$.

Let us define the complex coordinate on the plane $z = x + i\tau$. Then we can perform the conformal transformation

$$w = \ln(z) = \ln(|z|) + i\theta = u + iv \quad (97)$$

that maps the entire plane onto an infinite cylinder with $-\infty < \text{Re}w < +\infty$ and of circumference 2π . The interface is mapped onto the two lines $v = \pi/2$ and $v = 3\pi/2$, while A is mapped onto $v = 0$ and $v = 2\pi \sim v = 0$.

We also implement a UV cut-off ϵ and an IR cut-off L , such that $\epsilon \leq |z| \leq L \implies \ln(\epsilon) \leq \text{Re}(w) \leq \ln(L)$. The strip now becomes of finite length $W := \ln(L/\epsilon)$.

The next step is to take periodic boundary conditions also for the u coordinate, so that $w \sim \ln(L/\epsilon)$ and the cylinder becomes a torus. [9, 6] This is to simplify the calculation further, and we will show in Appendix B that the boundary condition does not affect the

Figure 11: Logarithmic change of coordinates. The plane is mapped onto a strip of length $\ln(L/\epsilon)$ and height 2π for one copy, $2n\pi$ for n copies. These sides are then identified and the strip becomes a torus.

leading term of the entanglement entropy.
The partition function on the torus is

$$Z = \text{Tr} \left(I_{LR} q^{H_{CFT_R}} I_{LR}^\dagger q^{H_{CFT_L}} \right) \quad \text{with } q = e^{-2\pi^2/W} \quad (98)$$

with the evolution direction being along the v axis. Indeed, we are picturing a CFT defined at $v = 0$ along the entire length of the cylinder. This CFT, which corresponds to the CFT_L , is evolved along the v direction by the respective Hamiltonian, H_L , until it encounters the interface I_{LR} . After this, the system is changed to the CFT_R , as the two communicate through I_{LR} , and the evolution is now described by H_R . Again, the system evolves with this Hamiltonian until it encounters the interface again, and switches to the other CFT.

To compute the Rényi entropies, we take n copies of the system glued along A , the positive real axis in the z -plane. As a result, we have n copies of the strip in the w surface, glued together along $v = 2\pi, 4\pi, \dots, 2n\pi$. There are also $2n$ interfaces and the circumference of the cylinder is now $2n\pi$.

The partition function becomes

$$Z_n = \text{Tr} \left(I_{LR} q^{H_{CFT_R}} I_{LR}^\dagger q^{H_{CFT_L}} \right)^n . \quad (99)$$

See Appendix A for an explicit derivation.

Equation 99 holds when we take the v direction as the direction of revolution¹⁵, but we can also decide to evolve the system along the u direction, so that

$$Z_n = \text{Tr} \left(e^{-H_n W} \right) . \quad (100)$$

H_n is now the Hamiltonian that describes the new CFT that lives on the circumference of the cylinder. It is composed of both the CFTs, each present n times, and they are interspersed with each other every π , after an interface insertion.

In the limit $W \gg 1$ the main contribution is given by the ground state, so

¹⁵On the torus, the Hamiltonian is rotating the system along the circumference.

$$Z_n = \text{Tr} (e^{-H_n W}) \approx e^{-E_n^0 W} \quad (101)$$

where E_n^0 is the ground state energy of the system defined on the circumference above. The Rényi entropies are then

$$\begin{aligned} S_A^{(n)} &= \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \left(\frac{\text{Tr}(\rho_A^n)}{\text{Tr}^n(\rho_A)} \right) = \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \left(\frac{Z_n}{Z_1^n} \right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \left(\frac{e^{-E_n^0 W}}{e^{-nE_1^0 W}} \right) = \frac{nE_1^0 - E_n^0}{1-n} W = \\ &:= \frac{c_{eff}}{12} \frac{1+n}{n} W \end{aligned} \quad (102)$$

where we have defined [29, 18]

$$c_{eff} = \frac{12n}{1-n^2} (nE_1^0 - E_n^0) \quad (103)$$

which is called the "effective central charge". This new constant is highly dependent on the theory and very non-trivial. Usually it is not calculated explicitly, but it is an important generalization of the central charge when dealing with interface CFTs.

Note that this definition is slightly different from the one in [17] since in the latter a rescaling of the cylinder circumference was performed from $2n\pi$ to 2π . Thus the energy of the ground state itself is rescaled, and it is E_n^0/n .

The entanglement entropy in the presence of the interface is therefore

$$S_A = \frac{c_{eff}}{6} \ln \frac{L}{\epsilon} . \quad (104)$$

4.4.2 Defect twist operator

We present here another approach we have employed to describe the interface CFT and its Rényi entropies, more similar to the one provided by Cardy in [7]. Indeed, we want to recover the formalism of the twist operators even in the presence of an interface. With the defect inserted, the two-point function of the twist operators changes. Moreover, we want to study a set-up similar to the one in the previous section, where the entangling surface reaches the interface. This implies that the bulk twist operator must be expanded with a defect OPE, and our aim is to define it and find the operators and corresponding scaling dimensions involved. Consider the twist operators positioned at $\Phi_n(x_1, t_1)$ and $\Phi_{-n}(x_2, t_2)$. We take the entangling surface perpendicular to the interface, so $t_1 = t_2 = t$, and the two-point function is

$$\langle \Phi_n(x_1, t) \Phi_{-n}(x_2, t) \rangle = \frac{1}{(|x_1||x_2|)^{\Delta_n}} f \left(\frac{(x_1 - x_2)^2}{|x_1||x_2|} \right) . \quad (105)$$

To understand what happens at the interface, we need to move Φ_n close to it. This operation leads to an expansion of Φ_n in terms of its defect OPE, which has the general form

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_n(x_1, t) \xrightarrow{x_1 \rightarrow 0} & b_{n\hat{1}} |x_1|^{-\Delta_n} \hat{\mathbb{1}}(t) + b_{n\hat{n}} |x_1|^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n} \hat{\Phi}_n(t) + \\ & + b_{n\partial\hat{n}} |x_1|^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n + 1} \partial \hat{\Phi}_n(t) + \dots \underset{x_1 \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \\ & b_{n\hat{1}} |x_1|^{-\Delta_n} \hat{\mathbb{1}}(t) + b_{n\hat{n}} |x_1|^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n} \hat{\Phi}_n(t). \end{aligned} \quad (106)$$

$\hat{\Phi}_n$ is the first non-trivial operator on the interface that encodes the twist. As it is the leading term after the identity, it is the one with the smallest scaling dimension that encodes the twist.

We need two twist operators to pass across the copies consistently, because for every passage from one sheet to another, we need to be able to invert the operation. With the identity, we cannot jump from one Riemann sheet to another; thus, we obtain a piece of CFT data, because it must be $b_{n\hat{1}} = a_n = 0$.

Now 105 can be expanded as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Phi_n(x_1, t) \Phi_{-n}(x_2, t) \rangle & \xrightarrow{x_1 \rightarrow 0} \\ & b_{n\hat{n}} |x_1|^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n} \langle \hat{\Phi}_n(t) \Phi_{-n}(x_2, t) \rangle + \mathcal{O}\left(x_1^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n + 1}\right) = \\ & = \frac{b_{n\hat{n}}}{(|x_1||x_2|)^{\Delta_n - \hat{\Delta}_n} (x_2)^{2\hat{\Delta}_n}} + \mathcal{O}\left(x_1^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n + 1}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (107)$$

In general, there are other operators contributing, whether they are primary fields or not. Here we consider the one with the smallest scaling dimension, which gives the leading term in the $x_1 \rightarrow 0$ limit.

By definition,

$$\text{Tr}(\rho_A^n) \propto \langle \hat{\Phi}_n(t) \Phi_{-n}(x_2, t) \rangle \quad (108)$$

and the Rényi entropies are

$$\begin{aligned} S_A^{(n)} & = \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \frac{b_{n\hat{n}}}{(|x_1||x_2|)^{\Delta_n - \hat{\Delta}_n} (x_2)^{2\hat{\Delta}_n}} = \\ & = \frac{1}{1-n} \left[\ln(b_{n\hat{n}}) + (\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n) \ln(|x_1||x_2|) - 2\hat{\Delta}_n \ln(|x_2|) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (109)$$

The defect OPE holds for every interface and every CFT, since it depends only on the operators that are inserted. To find the entanglement entropy, we want to take the leading term of the expansion in the limit $L \rightarrow \infty$.

The second term, proportional to $\ln(|x_1||x_2|)$, is divergent in the limit $x_1 \rightarrow 0$. If we take the limit $x_2 \rightarrow \infty$ as well, we can regularize both UV and IR divergences by imposing the corresponding cut-offs $x_1 = \epsilon$ and $x_2 = L = 1/\epsilon$. Then, $\ln(|x_1||x_2|) \rightarrow \ln(1) = 0$.

The third term is

$$S_A^{(n)} = \frac{2}{n-1} \hat{\Delta}_n \ln \frac{L}{\epsilon} . \quad (110)$$

where we have multiplied the argument of the logarithm by $1/\epsilon$ to make it dimensionless. This is the leading term, since it behaves as the logarithm of L , while the term proportional to $\ln b_{n\hat{n}}$ is a constant and is suppressed. Comparing this with 102, we can finally find

$$\hat{\Delta}_n = \frac{c_{eff}}{24} \left(n - \frac{1}{n} \right) . \quad (111)$$

Compared to the scaling dimension of the bulk twist operator Δ_n , the central charge is replaced by the effective central charge, and there is an additional factor of $1/2$ overall.

5 Entanglement Entropy and energy transmission

Energy transmission and entanglement entropy are two important tools for investigating interface CFTs. They are highly non-trivial and provide us with important information about the theories and the interface itself. It is natural to ask whether these two properties can be related.

It has already been shown that $c_{eff} \leq \min(c_L, c_R)$ in [18] for generic two-dimensional CFTs, while we have already shown that $c_{LR} \leq \min(c_L, c_R)$. Recently, a relation between the effective central charge and the constant c_{LR} has been stated in two-dimensional conformal field theories. In particular, [17]

$$c_{eff} \geq c_{LR} . \quad (112)$$

The new bound has been proven for specific set-ups in [17]¹⁶, but not in general. If true, it would imply that the amount of energy transmitted never exceeds the amount of information transmitted. This statement must be understood in the context of a quasi-particle picture, where EPR pairs are created and propagate, and some end up with one particle in \bar{A} and one in A . Thus, there is an increase in the energy of A , but the entanglement entropy also increases. This result could have important consequences in the study of quantum information and condensed matter systems.

In [17], the proof is found through holographic tools. That is also why it could only be proven for holographic CFTs, but these do not include all possible conformal theories. In this work, we take steps toward relating the two coefficients using only general conformal properties that hold for any CFT. In particular, we study an already existing relation between energy

¹⁶It has been proven for holographic CFTs and free CFTs.

and entropy, the Bekenstein bound, generalized to any QFT by Casini. This bound is true for every quantum field theory, and therefore for conformal theories.

In the next sections, we present the bound we want to study and calculate the quantities involved in our specific set-up: a two-dimensional conformal field theory with an entangling surface that extends into the positive half-plane and an interface placed on the time axis. Our belief is that a clue about the new bound may be hidden there, and the apparent contrast disappears when taking into account the contribution of the vacuum state in 112.

In this work, we will calculate the left-hand side of the Casini bound and find that it depends on c_{eff} as we expected. The right-hand side is left for future work.

5.1 Bekenstein bound and Casini generalization

The Bekenstein bound is [2, 11]

$$S \leq \lambda ER \tag{113}$$

with S being the entropy, E the energy, and R the typical size of a certain region in space-time where the energy is confined. λ is a constant of order one.

It was formulated in the context of black hole thermodynamics and arises from the following considerations. Consider a thought experiment where a system with mass m and entropy S is dropped into a Schwarzschild black hole of mass M , where $M \gg m$. The initial entropy of the black hole is given by the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy $S_{BH} = (\hbar c)^{-1} 4\pi GM^2$. We neglect energy losses from gravitational and Hawking radiation, which are minimal due to the large mass M . After absorbing the system, the mass of the black hole increases to $M + m$ and the entropy increases by $(\hbar c)^{-1} 8\pi GMm$ plus a negligible term of order m^2 . The generalized second law [1] requires that the total entropy, which includes both the entropy outside the black hole and the black hole entropy, can never decrease, that is,

$$-S + 8\pi \frac{GMm}{\hbar c} \geq 0.$$

Imagine making the black hole's radius smaller and smaller, but still large enough compared to the system's radius R so that the system can still be absorbed by the hole.¹⁷ Given the Schwarzschild black hole radius $r_h = 2GM/c^2$, we obtain equation 113 with $E = mc^2$. [2]

Despite its formulation, the Bekenstein bound does not contain any information on the gravitational theory behind it, and so it was proposed to be true for a generic region in flat space. Therefore, in principle, it can be generalized for a generic QFT.

Casini has proven that [11]

¹⁷This condition is consistent with m being much smaller than M .

$$S(\rho_V) - S(\rho_V^0) \leq \langle K_V \rangle - \langle K_V \rangle_0 \quad (114)$$

holds for every QFT. Here, ρ_V is the density matrix of a region of space V , and the superscript 0 indicates evaluation in the vacuum. K is the modular Hamiltonian of the region V , and it is evaluated in the excited and vacuum states, defined by ρ_V and ρ_V^0 respectively. This bound was proposed and demonstrated to be a generalization of the Bekenstein bound to a generic QFT in [11].

Let us discuss this generalization. First, we note that the left-hand side of the Bekenstein bound is here replaced by the difference between the entanglement entropy of a generic (excited) state and the vacuum state. The entanglement entropy, if related to a mixed state, also takes into account the entropy related to the uncertainty of a measurement. The difference between the excited state and vacuum entropy is a finite quantity: in fact, the divergent terms, which in our two-dimensional case are both proportional to $\ln(1/\epsilon)$, cancel out.

The right-hand side of the bound is now replaced by the expectation value of the modular Hamiltonian, which is a generalization of the energy in V . We cannot calculate the energy of a localized region in other ways, because the Hamiltonian operator refers to the entire system and is defined only on the total Hilbert space. The modular Hamiltonian K is defined as [11, 9]

$$\rho_V^0 = \frac{e^{-K}}{\text{Tr}e^{-K}}. \quad (115)$$

Take V to be a half-spatial plane of a generic QFT. If the system is localized and has size L at a distance R from the boundary of V , such that $R \gtrsim L$, the expression for $\langle K \rangle$ is known and is $\langle K \rangle \sim 2\pi ER$. When V is a sphere of radius R in a generic CFT and the state is localized at its center, then $\langle K \rangle \sim \pi ER$. Thus, $\langle K \rangle$ is proposed as a generalization of the rhs of the Bekenstein bound.

Also in this case there are divergences near the boundary of V , plus for a constant shift in K the density matrix does not change. That is why we again consider the difference between an excited state and the vacuum state.

To prove equation (114), we recall that $\langle K_V \rangle - \langle K_V \rangle_0 = \text{Tr}(K\rho_V) - \text{Tr}(K\rho_V^0)$. By definition, $K = -\ln\rho_V^0 - \ln(\text{Tr}e^{-K})$. Using explicitly the definition of entanglement entropy, equation (114) becomes

$$\text{Tr}(\rho_V \ln\rho_V) - \text{Tr}(\rho_V \ln\rho_V^0) \geq 0. \quad (116)$$

This is just the relative entropy $S(\rho_V|\rho_V^0)$, which is non-negative. This is the proof of the Casini bound.

In the next section, we evaluate the entanglement entropy in an excited state via the twist operator formalism. This, together with the vacuum result in section 4.4, will give the left-

hand side of the Casini bound for our set-up.

Note that equation (112) seems to be in contrast to the Bekenstein bound.

5.2 Entanglement Entropy in excited states

The goal is to relate the effective central charge, which is involved in the entanglement entropy across an interface, and c_{LR} , which governs the energy transmission coefficient. A possible strategy is to evaluate the entanglement entropy for the same set-up as in section 4.4.2, but in an excited state.

To create the excitation, we need to insert a (scalar) operator into the theory, which in general is a primary or quasi-primary operator that will create left- and right-moving bumps, as described in section 3.3. The difference is that the theory now lives on an n -sheeted Riemann surface, so this operation is not trivial. Indeed, the insertion must be placed in each sheet; thus, the total operator is a multiple-copy operator

$$\mathcal{O}(z) = \bigotimes_{i=1}^n O^{(i)}(z) = \underbrace{O^{(1)}(z) \otimes O^{(2)}(z) \otimes \cdots \otimes O^{(n)}(z)}_{n \text{ terms}} . \quad (117)$$

Then, what we would like to find is the expectation value of the twist operators in the state created by \mathcal{O}

$$\langle \mathcal{O} | \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) | \mathcal{O} \rangle , \quad (118)$$

which reduces to the evaluation of the correlation function

$$\langle \mathcal{O}(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \mathcal{O}(z_4) \rangle . \quad (119)$$

Our case of study is when the excitation is created in the left CFT, and the entangling surface lies along the entire right CFT at $t = 0$. The entangling surface reaches the interface, so we will take the limit $\Phi_n(z_1 = (x_1, y_1)) \rightarrow \hat{\Phi}_n(0, y_1)$, and this will extract information about c_{eff} .

5.2.1 Single-copy stress tensor excitation

We first treat the case of a single-copy operator insertion. This will help us understand how to evaluate correlation functions on one sheet. Indeed, we will show that it is possible to expand the multiple-copy operators involved in an OPE that reduces the problem to the calculation of a single operator insertion.

Similarly to what was done in 5, we create the excitation with a holomorphic operator, so that only the right-moving bump will be present. Let us choose the stress tensor, which always exists in every CFT.

Figure 12: Integrals involved in the calculation of the correlation function of two stress tensors and two twist fields on one sheet. Here, the procedure for the stress tensor inserted at z_1 is displayed. For the second stress tensor, the procedure is similar, but the presence of the identity operator at z_1 must be considered.

Since we create the state in the left CFT, we are using T_L . The corresponding correlation function is

$$\langle T_L(z_1)\Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2)\Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3)T_L(z_4) \rangle . \quad (120)$$

Since the twist fields are scalar primaries, we would like to use equation 30 and rewrite the above expression as a sum of differential operations on the two-point function $\langle \Phi_n(z_2)\Phi_{-n}(z_3) \rangle$. Let us first consider the stress tensor positioned at z_1 . It can be written in the integral form $\oint dw_1 (2\pi i)^{-1} T_L(w_1)/(w_1 - z_1)$. The four-point function can be translated into a sum of three contributions, where the integral is performed around the three other insertions at z_2 , z_3 , and z_4 . The contribution given by the evaluation around z_4 is

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2)\Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \left[\oint_{w_4} \frac{dw_1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{w_1 - z_4} T_L(w_1)T_L(z_4) \right] \rangle = \\ & = \frac{c_L/2}{(z_1 - z_4)^4} \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2)\Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle + \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{(z_1 - z_4)^2} \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2)\Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3)T_L(z_4) \rangle + \\ & \quad + \frac{\partial_4}{z_1 - z_4} \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2)\Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3)T_L(z_4) \rangle . \end{aligned} \quad (121)$$

We now have to consider the action of $T_L(w_1)$ on the twist operators. These are positioned in the right CFT, so the integration contour encounters the interface first. On the interface, Cardy's gluing condition holds, $T_L(w) = \bar{T}_L(\bar{w}) + T_R(w) - \bar{T}_R(\bar{w})$, so we can analytically continue $T_L(w_1)$ to the other side of the interface using this expression. In fact, T_L is only defined in the left theory, and so we have to analytically continue it into the right CFT.

To understand how to do this, let us rotate our system and consider the interface placed horizontally. In this way, the path of the integral is real, and it is easier to consider z and \bar{z} . The left CFT is now above the horizontal interface, and the right is below. Then z_1 and z_4 are above, and z_2 and z_3 are below.¹⁸ The integral now goes along the interface from $w = -\infty$ to $w = +\infty$. Since \bar{T}_L depends on \bar{w} , it is defined below the interface, where \bar{w} lives. Nevertheless, \bar{z}_2 and \bar{z}_3 are above, so there is no term deriving from the integral of \bar{T}_L . Let us now consider T_R and \bar{T}_R . Similarly, T_R is defined below the interface, and \bar{T}_R is above. This time, they both give contributions. In particular, the integral with T_R is closed clockwise, so it has a negative sign in front, while the integral with \bar{T}_R is closed anticlockwise. Because of the relative sign in the Cardy condition, they end up having the same sign in the final result. In particular, with T_R closed downward, we only have the poles coming from the OPE expansion, while with \bar{T}_R we have one more pole, the one at z_1 . It means that

¹⁸It also means that \bar{z}_1 and \bar{z}_4 are below, and \bar{z}_2 and \bar{z}_3 are above.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\langle \left\{ \left[\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{dw_1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{w_1 - z_1} T_R(w_1) \right] \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \right\} T_L(z_4) \right\rangle = \\
& = - \left(-\frac{h_n}{(z_2 - z_1)^2} + \frac{\partial_2}{z_2 - z_1} - \frac{h_n}{(z_3 - z_1)^2} + \frac{\partial_3}{z_3 - z_1} \right) \\
& \quad \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) T_L(z_4) \rangle = \quad (122) \\
& = - \left(-\frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_1 - z_2)^2} + \frac{\partial_2}{z_1 - z_2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_1 - z_3)^2} + \frac{\partial_3}{z_1 - z_3} \right) \\
& \quad \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) T_L(z_4) \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \left\langle \left\{ \left[\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{dw_1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{w_1 - z_1} \bar{T}_R(w_1) \right] \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \right\} T_L(z_4) \right\rangle = \\
& = - \left(-\frac{\bar{h}_n}{(\bar{z}_2 - z_1)^2} - \frac{\bar{\partial}_2}{\bar{z}_2 - z_1} - \frac{\bar{h}_n}{(\bar{z}_3 - z_1)^2} - \frac{\bar{\partial}_3}{\bar{z}_3 - z_1} \right) \\
& \quad \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) T_L(z_4) \rangle + \quad (123) \\
& \quad - \langle \bar{T}_R(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) T_L(z_4) \rangle = \\
& = - \left(-\frac{\Delta_n/2}{(\bar{z}_2 - z_1)^2} - \frac{\bar{\partial}_2}{\bar{z}_2 - z_1} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(\bar{z}_3 - z_1)^2} - \frac{\bar{\partial}_3}{\bar{z}_3 - z_1} \right) \\
& \quad \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) T_L(z_4) \rangle + \\
& \quad - \langle \bar{T}_R(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) T_L(z_4) \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

If we now rotate everything by $\pi/2$ to return to the original set-up, we find that $z \rightarrow +iz$ and $\bar{z} \rightarrow -i\bar{z}$, so that $|\partial z'/\partial z|^2 = |\partial \bar{z}'/\partial \bar{z}|^2 = -1$, and $\partial \rightarrow -i\partial$ and $\bar{\partial} \rightarrow +i\bar{\partial}$, such that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\langle \left\{ \left[\int_{-i\infty}^{+i\infty} \frac{dw'_1}{2\pi i} \frac{1}{z'_1 - w'_1} T_L(w'_1) \right] \Phi_n(z'_2, \bar{z}'_2) \Phi_{-n}(z'_3, \bar{z}'_3) \right\} T_L(z'_4) \right\rangle = \\
& = - \left\{ \left(-\frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z'_1 - z'_2)^2} + \frac{\partial'_2}{z'_1 - z'_2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z'_1 - z'_3)^2} + \frac{\partial'_3}{z'_1 - z'_3} \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left(-\frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z'_1 + \bar{z}'_2)^2} + \frac{\bar{\partial}'_2}{z'_1 + \bar{z}'_2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z'_1 + \bar{z}'_3)^2} + \frac{\bar{\partial}'_3}{z'_1 + \bar{z}'_3} \right) \right\} \\
& \quad \langle \Phi_n(z'_2, \bar{z}'_2) \Phi_{-n}(z'_3, \bar{z}'_3) T_L(z'_4) \rangle + \\
& \quad - \langle \bar{T}_R(-\bar{z}'_4) \Phi_n(z'_2, \bar{z}'_2) \Phi_{-n}(z'_3, \bar{z}'_3) T_L(z'_4) \rangle \quad (124)
\end{aligned}$$

Now we should evaluate the three-point function $\langle \Phi_n \Phi_{-n} T_L \rangle$. We drop the notation z' for brevity, but we are now working with the vertically oriented interface. Using the same reasoning,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) T_L(z_4) \rangle = \\
& = - \left(\frac{\partial_2}{z_2 - z_4} + \frac{\bar{\partial}_2}{\bar{z}_2 + z_4} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_2 - z_4)^2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(\bar{z}_2 + z_4)^2} \right) \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle + \\
& - \left(\frac{\partial_3}{z_3 - z_4} + \frac{\bar{\partial}_3}{\bar{z}_3 + z_4} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_3 - z_4)^2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(\bar{z}_3 + z_4)^2} \right) \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \bar{} \rangle + \\
& - \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \bar{T}_R(-\bar{z}_4) \rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{125}$$

This suggests that the excitation we should consider is actually produced by the simultaneous insertion of a T_L on the left and a \bar{T}_R on the right. This is the excitation we can explicitly calculate from the OPE of the stress tensors with the twist fields. The state we need to consider is therefore $|s\rangle = T_L \bar{T}_R |0\rangle$.

Finally, we take the limit $\Phi_n \rightarrow \hat{\Phi}_n$, which leads to

$$\langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle \rightarrow \frac{\hat{b}_{n\hat{n}}}{(|z_2 + \bar{z}_2||z_3 + \bar{z}_3|)^{\Delta_n - \hat{\Delta}_n}} \frac{1}{|z_2 - z_3|^{2\hat{\Delta}_n}}. \tag{126}$$

We can see that the dependence on c_{eff} arises from the derivatives of the two-point function of the twist fields.

The defect OPE is taken only after evaluating the contributions given by the stress tensors; otherwise, we would have integral paths crossing the interface, and those integrals would not be well-defined. Indeed, we should take into account the OPE terms of the defect expansion depending on the cross-ratio $\xi = z_{23}\bar{z}_{23}/[(z_2 + \bar{z}_2)(z_3 + \bar{z}_3)]$ - see the next section. The term in the above equation is the leading one.

This is valid for one sheet. If we have more than one, we have to take into account the contributions given by each stress tensor. For an n -sheeted surface, there are $2n$ stress tensor insertions. The difficulties arise not only from the increasing number of derivatives, but also from the effects that each stress tensor has on the others, since the copies are glued together and operators can interact among the replicas.

A similar problem has been discussed in [4] for a boundary CFT. However, it was not possible to find an explicit function of n , and an analytical expression is found only in certain limits.

The strategy we will use now is to first consider the total stress tensors and study the cross-ratios involved in the four-point function. In fact, even though they are multiple-copy operators, they are still just two operators in the CFT n ; therefore, their correlation function with the twist fields will have the same expression as a four-point function in a generic interface CFT. Studying the cross-ratios, we find that they have the same behavior when considering the physical limit of the definition of the state or the OPE limit obtained by fusing

the stress tensors. Indeed, the state is defined through an auxiliary complexification of time $t \rightarrow t + i\varepsilon$, and the physical limit is for $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. We are then able to expand the total stress tensors with their OPE and, as we will see, the first term we are interested in is a correlator with one single-copy stress tensor inserted.

5.2.2 Multiple-copy stress tensor excitation

Since we are in a replicated theory, we need to consider multiple-copy operators. Indeed, if we create an excited state on the original CFT and then ask about the entropy of a certain subsystem, when employing the replica trick we need to replicate the entire CFT, including the excitation.

If the excitation is caused by the stress tensor inserted at z , it becomes the operator $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}(z) = \bigotimes_{i=1}^n T^{(i)}(z)$ in the CFT^n . As discussed before, the single-copy operators can interact between the replicas, and the explicit calculation of the point function through the holomorphic properties of T becomes rather complicated.

We need to change our strategy and study the correlation function from the point of view of the total manifold where we define the multiple-copy operators and the twist fields. Indeed, on the n -sheeted Riemann surface, $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}(z)$ is a single operator, and it will behave as such. Thus, we can study the cross-ratios of the correlation function as if we were in a theory defined only on one sheet. We will then perform some limits in order to constrain the correlation function and the OPE, and find some useful expressions for our study.

Now, as shown in the section above, the operator we are considering to create the state must be the combination of $T_L(z)$ and $\bar{T}_R(\bar{z})$ such that we will be able to find a result related to equation 125.

Before studying the cross-ratios, let us consider the operator content. As said, the state we want to study is generated by the insertions of T_L at z_1 and \bar{T}_R at $-\bar{z}_1$. It seems then that the correlation function of the twist operators in the excited state corresponds to a six-point function. However, the positions of T_L and \bar{T}_R are not independent, and their holomorphy also constrains them.

We can study the situation via the so-called "folding trick".

It consists of folding our theory along the interface, so that it becomes a boundary CFT, and everything on the right side is mapped to the left via $z \rightarrow -\bar{z}$. Then it is possible to study the original set-up as the boundary CFT of $\text{CFT}_L \otimes \overline{\text{CFT}}_R$.

In our particular case, \bar{T}_R is precisely mapped to z_1 , where T_L is placed, and into its holomorphic counterpart T_R . We can therefore define a new holomorphic operator $\mathcal{T} = T_L T_R$ such that $\mathcal{T}|0\rangle = T_L T_R|0\rangle$ in the folded theory, and study the four-point function $\langle \mathcal{T}(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \mathcal{T}(z_4) \rangle_B$. Note that this correlation function satisfies the same analytic properties as in the presence of an interface, with all the operators placed on the same side. Note also that here we already take into account the multiple-copy theory, so the scaling dimension of \mathcal{T} is $\Delta_{\mathcal{T}} = (2 + 2)n = 4n$.

Figure 13: After finding the expression 125, the state we take into consideration is the one created by the insertion of a T_L and a specular insertion of a \bar{T}_R with respect to the interface. Here, only the transmitted holomorphic and the reflected antiholomorphic bump are depicted for simplicity.

Figure 14: Folding trick: the right CFT is mapped onto the left CFT via the map $z \rightarrow -\bar{z}$, folding the theory at the interface. It can be seen that $\bar{T}_R(-\bar{z}_1) \rightarrow T_R(z_1)$, where T_L is also inserted. In the folded theory, we can therefore define the new operator $\mathcal{T} = T_L T_R$, which creates the state we are interested in, in the theory $\text{CFT}_L \otimes \overline{\text{CFT}}_R$ with a boundary at $x = 0$.

Figure 15: Using conformal transformations, we can freely move the positions of the operators. In particular, we can map one \mathcal{T} at the origin, one \mathcal{T} at infinity and fix the distance of one twist field from the origin.

Let us now study the degrees of freedom of the above four-point function. Let us first consider the most general case, where none of the operators involved is placed in any specific position, except for the constraint that the two twist fields are on the right side of the interface and the stress tensors on the left side. We will first work in Euclidean space-time, defining the coordinate on the plane as $z = x + i\tau$. Later, by analytically continuing the time coordinate with $\tau \rightarrow it$, the variables z and \bar{z} become real, with $z = x - t$ being the light-cone coordinate for right-moving and $\bar{z} = x + t$ for left-moving excitations. To understand how many degrees of freedom this function has, let us use the transformations from the symmetry group to fix some of them, that is, to fix the positions of the operators (see figure 15).

Note that the total stress tensor is holomorphic, so the physics does not depend on its distance from the interface (see section 3.4.1). In fact, because of holomorphy, once the correlator with T on the interface is known, it is also known with T off the interface by analytic continuation. This means that no dependence on new cross-ratios can arise when T is moved away from the interface. Hence, we can count cross-ratios by placing T on the interface. With one translation, one stress tensor can be fixed at the origin of the plane, and with one special conformal transformation the other can be mapped to the point at infinity. With one dilation, one twist field can be set to be at a fixed distance $r = 1$ from the origin. Rotations are no longer included in the group because of the presence of the defect.

The variables that remain unset are the phase of the first twist operator and both the radius and phase of the second twist field. Thus, there are three degrees of freedom left after using all the allowed transformations, and so there will be three independent cross-ratios in this correlator.

Typically, in a two-dimensional CFT, the cross-ratios involved in the four-point function are

$$\frac{|z_{12}|^2|z_{34}|^2}{|z_{13}|^2|z_{24}|^2} = \frac{|z_{14}|^2|z_{23}|^2}{|z_{13}|^2|z_{24}|^2} \quad (127)$$

where $z_{ij} = z_i - z_j$. The square modulus involves the product of the holomorphic and antiholomorphic coordinates $|z_{ij}|^2 = (z_i - z_j)(\bar{z}_i - \bar{z}_j)$. This is essential for them to be independent. Indeed, if we just take the ratio of the holomorphic distances, the second cross-ratio can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{z_{14}z_{23}}{z_{13}z_{24}} &= \frac{(z_{12} + z_{24})(z_{24} - z_{34})}{z_{13}z_{24}} = \\ &= \frac{z_{12}z_{24} - z_{12}z_{34} - z_{24}z_{34} + z_{24}^2}{z_{13}z_{24}} = \\ &= \frac{z_{24}(z_{12} + z_{24} - z_{34})}{z_{13}z_{24}} - \frac{z_{12}z_{34}}{z_{13}z_{24}} = \\ &= 1 - \frac{z_{12}z_{34}}{z_{13}z_{24}}. \end{aligned} \quad (128)$$

In fact, it is typically better to choose $(z_{12}z_{34})/(z_{13}z_{24})$ and $(\bar{z}_{12}\bar{z}_{34})/(\bar{z}_{13}\bar{z}_{24})$ as the independent ones. Since in our case there are two holomorphic stress tensors, the function cannot depend on \bar{z}_1 and \bar{z}_4 . Therefore, one cross-ratio can be $\chi = (z_{12}z_{34})/(z_{13}z_{24})$, but then we cannot take the other one.

There are many other possible candidates for our cross-ratios. The easiest way to find two independent ones is to pick two of them—wisely—and then check if they are independent, rather than finding the relations between all possible ratios. Let us take

$$\xi = \frac{z_{23}\bar{z}_{23}}{(z_2 + \bar{z}_2)(z_3 + \bar{z}_3)} \quad \eta = \frac{z_{14}\bar{z}_{23}}{(z_1 + \bar{z}_2)(z_4 + \bar{z}_3)}. \quad (129)$$

It can be easily seen that they are invariant under conformal transformations with respect to the interface. The first is the cross-ratio involved in the bulk-to-bulk two-point function in a defect CFT. Indeed, with the interface placed on the imaginary time axis, $z + \bar{z}$ is the component perpendicular to the defect, which now must be taken into account for the twist fields (see section 2.3). The ratio η is similar to the one we discarded, but with the antiholomorphic coordinate involved, so it is expected to be independent of χ .

Let us check the independence of χ, ξ and η . Certainly, χ and η are independent, since the second one depends on the \bar{z} coordinates. After the transformations shown above, the coordinates are mapped such that $z_1 = 0$, $z_4 \rightarrow \infty$ and $z_2 = 1/\bar{z}_2$. The cross-ratios take the form $\chi = z_4/z_3 - 1$, $\eta = z_3\bar{z}_4 - 1$ and $\xi = \frac{(z_3 - z_4)(1 - z_3\bar{z}_4)}{(z_3^2 - 1)(z_4 - \bar{z}_4)} = \frac{-\chi\eta}{(z_3^2 - 1)(1 + \chi - \bar{z}_4/z_3)}$. We can further fix χ and η by a specific choice of coordinates. If ξ is still not fixed, then it means that it is independent of the other two. For example, consider $z_3 = e^{i\theta}$ and $z_4 = 2e^{i\theta}$.

Then $\chi = 1$ and $\eta = 1$, but $\xi = |1 - e^{2i\theta}|^{-2}/2$. Since it still depends on θ , it is independent of χ and η .

Figure 16: Every position is now fixed apart from θ , which is the only remaining variable.

We can therefore use these three cross-ratios in our correlator.

The four-point function can be split into a kinematical term, which is completely fixed by conformal symmetry, and a dynamical term, which depends on the cross-ratios. For a four-point function, the kinematical term is in general [25]

$$K_4 = \frac{1}{(z_{12}^2)^{\frac{\Delta_1+\Delta_2}{2}} (z_{34}^2)^{\frac{\Delta_3+\Delta_4}{2}}} \left(\frac{z_{24}^2}{z_{14}^2} \right)^{\frac{\Delta_1-\Delta_2}{2}} \left(\frac{z_{14}^2}{z_{13}^2} \right)^{\frac{\Delta_3-\Delta_4}{2}}. \quad (130)$$

Instead, we can take our four-point correlation function in the presence of the defect as

$$\langle \mathcal{T}(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \mathcal{T}(z_4) \rangle = \frac{f(\chi, \eta, \xi)}{(z_{14})^{8n} (|z_2 + \bar{z}_2| |z_3 + \bar{z}_3|)^{\Delta_n}}. \quad (131)$$

Indeed, a correlator is in general a function of the operators' insertion positions, and it must change under a conformal transformation as

$$\langle O_1(z_1) \dots O_n(z_n) \rangle = \left| \frac{\partial z'_1}{\partial z_1} \right|^{\Delta_1} \dots \left| \frac{\partial z'_n}{\partial z_n} \right|^{\Delta_n} \langle O_1(z'_1) \dots O_n(z'_n) \rangle.$$

Let us rename the correlator $\langle O_1(z_1) \dots O_n(z_n) \rangle = G(z_1, \dots, z_n)$. Many functions satisfy the above expression. We can always rewrite G as the product of two other functions

Figure 17: Left: The power-law tails of the radiation might hit the interface at a time greater than zero, and so they would miss the entangling region. Taking the limit $d \rightarrow \infty$, this problem is avoided. Right: The entangling region must go to infinity faster than d ; otherwise, the radiation will be missed. In both figures, we depict only the holomorphic bump for simplicity.

$G(z_1, \dots, z_n) = P(z_1, \dots, z_n)f(\xi_i)$, the first which changes with the Jacobian to the right power, and the second which depends on the cross-ratios, which are conformal invariant objects. P is arbitrary (up to the transformation rule) and its choice will influence the form of f . Therefore, we can always take P as the product of functions that we know change correctly with the Jacobians under conformal transformations.

In this case, where there are two insertions of a holomorphic operator and two bulk operators in the presence of a defect (or boundary), it is convenient to choose the product of the two-point function of the holomorphic operators and the one-point functions of the bulk operators: $\langle \mathcal{T}(z_1)\Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2)\Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3)\mathcal{T}(z_4) \rangle \sim \langle \mathcal{T}(z_1)\mathcal{T}(z_4) \rangle \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \rangle \langle \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle f(\chi, \eta, \xi)$.

Let us now consider what is happening physically in Minkowski space-time. We analytically continue the complex coordinate in Euclidean space-time by performing the Wick rotation $\tau \rightarrow it$, which implies $z = x + i\tau \rightarrow x - t$ and $\bar{z} = x + t$. An excitation is created by the stress tensor at the point $x_1 - t_1 = d$, where d is a real positive number. We consider this insertion so that the holomorphic bump produced propagates along the direction $t = x - d$, similarly to figure 6, intercepting the time axis, and thus the interface, at $t = -d$. If we then consider the entangling surface to be the right-half real axis at time $t = 0$, we are sure to collect all the transmitted radiation. It is important to notice that, in order to have all the transmitted radiation collected, it must be $L = z_3 \gg z_1, z_4$ — see figure 17. The hierarchy of infinities, with z_3 being much greater than the stress tensor insertions, must be taken into account when evaluating the limits of the cross-ratios.

Thus, the state on the right at $t = 0$ will be affected by the excitation. To make the state normalizable, the insertion must be placed more precisely at $z = x - t + i\varepsilon$, such that

Figure 18: Insertion of T such that the final state is normalizable, through the auxiliary complexification of time. Here we depict only the holomorphic insertion of T_L .

$$|\mathcal{T}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\langle \mathcal{T}(x, t - i\varepsilon) \mathcal{T}(x, t + i\varepsilon) \rangle}} \mathcal{T}(x, t + i\varepsilon) |0\rangle \quad (132)$$

and ε is a real positive number.

When evaluating $\langle \mathcal{T} | \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) | \mathcal{T} \rangle$ as a four-point function, the difference in the positions of the stress tensors is $z_{14} = 2i\varepsilon$. Collecting all the transmitted radiation suggests taking the limit $x - t = d \rightarrow \infty$, which means the \mathcal{T} s are placed far away from the interface. This is due to the power-law tails of the bump. To ensure the beam is entirely collected, it must be generated far away from the interface. It is then convenient to take $1 - \chi$ instead of χ , so that

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \chi &= 1 - \frac{z_{12} z_{34}}{z_{13} z_{24}} \xrightarrow{z_3 \rightarrow \infty} 1 - \frac{z_{12}}{z_{42}} \xrightarrow{z_1, z_4 \rightarrow \infty} 0 \\ \eta &= \frac{z_{14} \bar{z}_{23}}{(z_1 + \bar{z}_2)(z_4 + \bar{z}_3)} \xrightarrow{z_3 \rightarrow \infty} -\frac{z_{14}}{z_1 + \bar{z}_2} \xrightarrow{\substack{z_1, z_4 \rightarrow \infty \\ z_{14} \text{ finite}}} 0 \\ \xi &= \frac{z_{23} \bar{z}_{23}}{(z_2 + \bar{z}_2)(z_3 + \bar{z}_3)} \xrightarrow{z_3 \rightarrow \infty} +\infty. \end{aligned} \quad (133)$$

We can then take the fusion of the stress tensors and replace them with their OPE. Indeed, the cross-ratios tend to the same limits in the Euclidean analysis when $z_1 \rightarrow z_4$, $z_2 \rightarrow -\bar{z}_2$, and $z_3 \rightarrow -\bar{z}_3$; that is, when the twist operators approach the interface. This means that

Figure 19: Graphical representation of how the stress tensors are fused. Here three replicas are drawn. The first OPE term is obtained when all the tensors fuse into the identity, and the second when, on one sheet, we take the stress tensor itself. We sum it over the replicas because it can happen at any sheet and it has the same expansion order. More terms are present after that, but they are subleading.

the dynamical function $f(1 - \chi, \eta, \xi)$ behaves as $f(0, 0, \infty)$ in both these limits. Hence, it is possible to evaluate the limit in the Lorentzian configuration through the classical OPE in Euclidean space.

The OPE we are interested in is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{T}(z + \tilde{\varepsilon})\mathcal{T}(z - \tilde{\varepsilon}) &\underset{\tilde{\varepsilon} \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \\
 \tilde{\varepsilon}^{-8n} &\left((c_L/2)^n \mathbb{1}^{\otimes n} + 2 (c_L/2)^{n-1} \tilde{\varepsilon}^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\mathbb{1}^{\otimes i-1} \otimes T_L^{(i)}(z) \otimes \mathbb{1}^{\otimes n-i} + \right. \right. \\
 &\left. \left. + \mathbb{1}^{\otimes i-1} \otimes \bar{T}_R^{(i)}(\bar{z}) \otimes \mathbb{1}^{\otimes n-i} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\tilde{\varepsilon}^3) \right). \quad (134)
 \end{aligned}$$

The constant $(c_L/2)^n$ comes from the fusion of the stress tensors on each plane.

The leading term is the identity, which has scaling dimension 0. However, this gives the partition function and the entanglement entropy of the vacuum state, which is subtracted when considering the Casini bound. A more detailed analysis is performed later.

The second term is obtained when, on the Riemann surface, all the T 's are fused into the identity, except for on one sheet.

If it is assumed that T is the lightest holomorphic operator, this is the first non-trivial leading term of the expansion. There are other terms after this, for example, a holomorphic operator with a higher scaling dimension or the non-trivial fusion of T 's on two sheets. However, these are suppressed in the limit $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, so we are not considering them in this analysis. We can thus evaluate the four-point function via the correlator of a single-copy stress tensor with the twist operators, as in equation 125. There are no more interactions with other T 's in the OPE limit, so it is possible to find an analytical expression for the entanglement entropy. Then, one twist operator approaches the interface at $x = 0$ (regularized by the UV cutoff ϵ such that $x_2 \rightarrow \epsilon$), and the other goes to infinity (regularized by the IR cut-off L such that $x_3 \rightarrow L$). Since the theory is conformal, there always exists a conformal transformation that

Figure 20: Mapping from the plane to the sphere. The point at infinity is mapped to the north pole, so that both twist fields approach the interface.

maps the entire plane onto a sphere, such that the point at infinity is mapped to the north pole of the sphere.

As the interface also goes to infinity, it is possible to see through this map that the second twist field also reaches the interface, and thus it can be expanded with its defect OPE. Alternatively, we can also see that both the limits $z_3 \rightarrow \infty$ and $z_3 \rightarrow 0$ send $\xi \rightarrow \infty$, so f is fixed in the same way in either case. Thus we have ¹⁹

$$\begin{aligned}
& \langle \mathcal{T}(z_1 + i\varepsilon) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \mathcal{T}(z_4 = z_1 - i\varepsilon) \rangle \underset{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \\
& \sim \varepsilon^{-8n} \left(\frac{c_L^n}{2^n} \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle + \frac{c_L^{n-1}}{2^n} \varepsilon^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \langle T^{(i)}(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \right) = \\
& = \frac{c_L^n}{2^n} \varepsilon^{-8n} \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{c_L} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\langle T^{(i)}(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle}{\langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \right). \tag{135}
\end{aligned}$$

It must be normalized by the state norm $\langle \mathcal{T}(z_1 + i\varepsilon) \mathcal{T}(z_1 - i\varepsilon) \rangle \underset{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0}{\sim} (c/2)^n \varepsilon^{-8n}$. The Rényi entropies are then

$$\begin{aligned}
S_A^{(n)} &= \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle + \\
& + \frac{1}{1-n} \ln \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{c_L} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\langle T^{(i)}(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle}{\langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \right). \tag{136}
\end{aligned}$$

¹⁹Here and later $T^{(i)}$ is intended as in equation 134 as the contributions of the left holomorphic and right specular antiholomorphic stress tensors.

The first term is the vacuum entropy, and it is subtracted in the Casini bound. As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, it is possible to further develop the logarithm and obtain

$$S_A^{(n)} - S_{A,0}^{(n)} \underset{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \frac{1}{1-n} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{c_L} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\langle T^{(i)}(z_1) \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle}{\langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3). \quad (137)$$

When both twist fields approach the interface, their two-point function becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Phi_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \Phi_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle &\underset{z_2 \rightarrow 0, z_3 \rightarrow \infty}{\sim} \\ b_{n\hat{n}}^2 \left(\left| \frac{z_2 + \bar{z}_2}{2} \right| \left| \frac{z_3 + \bar{z}_3}{2} \right| \right)^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n} &\langle \hat{\Phi}_n(z_2, \bar{z}_2) \hat{\Phi}_{-n}(z_3, \bar{z}_3) \rangle = \\ = b_{n\hat{n}}^2 \left(\left| \frac{z_2 + \bar{z}_2}{2} \right| \left| \frac{z_3 + \bar{z}_3}{2} \right| \right)^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n} &\frac{1}{|z_2 - z_3|^{\hat{\Delta}_n}} \end{aligned} \quad (138)$$

In the numerator of equation 137, this limit must be performed after the action of T on the operators; otherwise, the analytical continuation of T_L in terms of T_R is not well-defined (see section 5.2.1). Thus, referring to 125,

$$\begin{aligned} S_A^{(n)} - S_{A,0}^{(n)} &\sim \frac{-1}{1-n} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{c_L} \cdot \\ &\cdot \left[\left(\frac{\partial_2}{z_2 - z_1} + \frac{\bar{\partial}_2}{z_1 + \bar{z}_2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_2 - z_1)^2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_1 + \bar{z}_2)^2} + \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{\partial_3}{z_3 - z_1} + \frac{\bar{\partial}_3}{z_1 + \bar{z}_3} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_3 - z_1)^2} - \frac{\Delta_n/2}{(z_1 + \bar{z}_3)^2} \right) \cdot \right. \\ &\quad \left. \cdot \frac{(|z_2 + \bar{z}_2||z_3 + \bar{z}_3|)^{\hat{\Delta}_n - \Delta_n}}{(z_2 - z_3)^{\hat{\Delta}_n/2} (\bar{z}_2 - \bar{z}_3)^{\hat{\Delta}_n/2}} \right] \cdot \\ &\cdot \frac{(|z_2 + \bar{z}_2||z_3 + \bar{z}_3|)^{-\hat{\Delta}_n + \Delta_n}}{(z_2 - z_3)^{-\hat{\Delta}_n/2} (\bar{z}_2 - \bar{z}_3)^{-\hat{\Delta}_n/2}} \end{aligned} \quad (139)$$

After some algebra, replacing $z_2 = \bar{z}_2 = \epsilon$, $z_3 = \bar{z}_3 = L$, and $z_1 = x - t$:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_A^{(n)} - S_{A,0}^{(n)} = \frac{1}{n-1} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{c_L} \left\{ (\Delta_n - \hat{\Delta}_n) \left[\frac{1}{2\varepsilon} \left(\frac{1}{x-t-\varepsilon} + \frac{1}{x-t+\varepsilon} \right) \right. \right. \\
\left. \left. + \frac{1}{2L} \left(\frac{1}{x-t-L} + \frac{1}{x-t+L} \right) \right] + \right. \\
\left. + \frac{\Delta_n}{2} \left(\frac{1}{(\varepsilon-x+t)^2} + \frac{1}{(L-x+t)^2} \right. \right. \\
\left. \left. + \frac{1}{(\varepsilon+x-t)^2} + \frac{1}{(L+x-t)^2} \right) + \right. \\
\left. + \frac{\hat{\Delta}_n}{2} \frac{-2d}{L-\varepsilon} \left(\frac{1}{(x-t)^2 - \varepsilon^2} - \frac{1}{(x-t)^2 - L^2} \right) \right\}. \tag{140}
\end{aligned}$$

Since ε is the UV cut-off, in the limit where it goes to zero, the leading term is

$$S_A^{(n)} - S_{A,0}^{(n)} \underset{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \frac{1}{n-1} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{c_L} \frac{\Delta_n - \hat{\Delta}_n}{\varepsilon(x-t)} = \frac{\varepsilon^2}{x-t} \frac{n+1}{12d\varepsilon} \left(\frac{c_R}{c_L} - \frac{c_{eff}}{2c_L} \right) \tag{141}$$

and the entanglement entropy is

$$S_A - S_{A,0} = \lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \left(S_A^{(n)} - S_{A,0}^{(n)} \right) \underset{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{12d} \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \left(\frac{c_R}{c_L} - \frac{c_{eff}}{2c_L} \right) \tag{142}$$

where we replaced $x-t = d$. A few remarks on this result: As a sanity check, we can see that the entanglement entropy is dimensionless, as it should be. The ε^2 dependence gives the order of the stress tensor OPE that is considered. The distance d tells where the stress tensor is placed. The quantity in the brackets has a minus sign in front of c_{eff} . This is remarkable since it may solve the tension between the Casini bound and the new bound proposed in [17].

Note that the cross-ratios reach the same limits by imposing $d \rightarrow \infty$ and $L \rightarrow \infty$, without making any assumption about ε . This suggests that the OPE and the entanglement entropy can be expressed in powers of $1/d$ instead of ε . This would be convenient since the state with $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ is no longer normalizable. However, we leave this analysis for future work.

This is then the left-hand side of the Casini bound for our set-up. The right-hand side still needs to be calculated and is left for future work.

6 Conclusions

The aim of this work was to find a general proof for equation 112 in two-dimensional CFTs. After reproducing some known results on conformal interfaces, energy transmission, and

entanglement entropy, we introduced a new operator, the defect twist operator, which encodes the entangling surface as it approaches the interface. We found that it has a scaling dimension with an expression very similar to the bulk twist operator, but proportional to c_{eff} :

$$\hat{\Delta}_n = \frac{c_{eff}}{24} \left(n - \frac{1}{n} \right) .$$

We then calculated the left-hand side of equation 114 for our specific set-up using the defect OPE of the twist fields and the defect twist operators. We found the entanglement entropy for an excited state created by the insertion of a stress tensor, which generates a holomorphic bump on the left of the interface; this propagates toward the right and is partially transmitted.

$$S_A - S_{A,0} \underset{\epsilon \rightarrow 0}{\sim} \frac{\epsilon^2}{12d} \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\frac{c_R}{c_L} - \frac{c_{eff}}{2c_L} \right) .$$

The entangling surface is on the right of the interface at $t = 0$. We find an expression that depends on c_{eff} and is a negative quantity. This is encouraging, since the two bounds seem to be in tension with each other. A negative quantity could solve the problem when considering the sign of the inequality 114 for this set-up.

The right-hand side of 114 is left for future work. Our belief is that the expression will contain c_{LR} , since the expectation value of the modular Hamiltonian depends on T_R and the state is created with T_L . Indeed, for a two-dimensional CFT without a defect, the modular Hamiltonian in the vacuum is given by

$$K_A \sim \int_0^{+\infty} dx x T_{00}(x, t) . \tag{143}$$

If the expression for a defected excited state is similar, we might be able to relate its expectation value to a correlation function with T_L and T_R , thereby obtaining a quantity where c_{LR} is involved.

A Torus partition function

Let us derive the partition function Z_n on the w -torus for the replicated theory.

The theory is composed of n copies of CFT_L and CFT_R , glued together by I . They evolve with \tilde{H}_L and \tilde{H}_R , respectively, along the (imaginary) v direction. These are not the original Hamiltonians because they are defined on the cylinder; this is why we denote them differently. To pass from one copy to the next, z rotates by an angle of 2π , which means that on the cylinder $\text{Im}(w)$ goes to $\text{Im}(w) + 2\pi$. Then each Hamiltonian evolves the corresponding CFT along the circumference for a time π .

Defining $\tilde{\beta} = 2\pi$, the single Hamiltonian evolution occurs for $\tilde{\beta}/2$. The partition function is

$$Z_n = \left\langle \left(I e^{-\frac{\tilde{\beta}}{2} \tilde{H}_R} I^\dagger e^{-\frac{\tilde{\beta}}{2} \tilde{H}_L} \right)^n \right\rangle. \quad (144)$$

We omit the subscripts of the operator I to lighten the notation.

Let us impose periodic boundary conditions on the real part of w , so that $\text{Re}(w) = \text{Re}(w) + \ln(L/\epsilon)$. Then the eigenvalues of the \tilde{H} operators are the energies of the states in the corresponding CFT defined on a circle of radius $R = \ln(L/\epsilon)/2\pi$. Z_n becomes

$$Z_n = \text{tr} \left(I e^{-\frac{\tilde{\beta}}{2} \tilde{H}_R} I^\dagger e^{-\frac{\tilde{\beta}}{2} \tilde{H}_L} \right)^n. \quad (145)$$

Z_n results in a sum over the eigenvalues of the eigenvectors of $\tilde{H}_{L,R}$. Since in radial quantization $H \propto L_0 + \bar{L}_0$, the energy levels on the unit radius circumference are the scaling dimensions of the operators of the theory, Δ , which create all possible states on the circumference. If E represents the eigenvalues of \tilde{H} , then $E = \Delta/R$ and

$$\tilde{H}_{L,R} = \frac{H_{L,R}}{R} = \frac{2\pi H_{L,R}}{\ln(L/\epsilon)} \quad (146)$$

Thus Z_n is

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n &= \text{tr} \left(I e^{-\pi H_L/R} I^\dagger e^{-\pi H_R/R} \right)^n = \\ &= \text{tr} \left(I e^{-2\pi^2 H_L/\ln(L/\epsilon)} I^\dagger e^{-2\pi^2 H_R/\ln(L/\epsilon)} \right)^n \end{aligned} \quad (147)$$

which is precisely equation 99 with $q = e^{-2\pi^2/W}$, where $W = \ln(L/\epsilon)$.

B Boundary conditions on the torus

Here we will show that the leading term of the entanglement entropy on the torus is the same regardless of the boundary conditions we impose [29, 10].

Consider first the theory without interfaces, and thus just one CFT, mapped onto the cylinder. Let us define the two boundary states $|a\rangle$ and $|b\rangle$ on the left and right edges of the

Figure 21: Cylinder with open or periodic boundary conditions.

cylinder, respectively. The torus is a cylinder where $|a\rangle = |b\rangle$.

Let us consider the Hamiltonian H_n which evolves along the u direction for a time W , which is the length of the cylinder.

Defining $\tilde{q} = e^{-2W}$, the partition function is

$$\begin{cases} Z_1^{cyl} = \tilde{q}^{-c/24} \sum_k \langle a|k\rangle \langle k|b\rangle \tilde{q}^{\Delta_k} \\ Z_n^{cyl} = \tilde{q}^{-c/24n} \sum_k \langle a|k\rangle \langle k|b\rangle \tilde{q}^{\Delta_k/n} \end{cases} \quad (148)$$

while on the torus it is

$$\begin{cases} Z_1^{tor} = \text{tr}(\rho_A) = \tilde{q}^{-c/24} \sum_k d_k \tilde{q}^{\Delta_k} \\ Z_n^{tor} = \text{tr}(\rho_A^n) = \tilde{q}^{-c/24n} \sum_k d_k \tilde{q}^{\Delta_k/n} . \end{cases} \quad (149)$$

Here, the Δ_k are the dimensions of the bulk operators and the d_k are the degeneracy factors [9].

In the limit $W \gg 1$, the ground state $|0\rangle$ is the only one contributing to the partition function. The ground state is generated by the identity operator, which has zero scaling dimension and no degeneracy.

After normalization, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr}(\rho_A^n)^{cyl} &\sim \frac{\tilde{q}^{-c/24n} \langle a|0\rangle \langle 0|b\rangle}{\tilde{q}^{-cn/24} (\langle a|0\rangle \langle 0|b\rangle)^n} \\ \text{tr}(\rho_A^n)^{tor} &\sim \frac{\tilde{q}^{-c/24n}}{\tilde{q}^{-cn/24}} \end{aligned} \quad (150)$$

and the Rényi entropies are

$$\begin{aligned} S_A^{(n) cyl} &\sim \frac{c}{12} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) W + g_a + g_b \\ S_A^{(n) tor} &\sim \frac{c}{12} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) W \end{aligned} \quad (151)$$

with $g_{a,b} = -\ln(\langle a, b|0\rangle)$. In the limit $W \gg 1$, the leading term is the same in both cases, so the boundary conditions are not relevant.

Now let us consider the set-up with interfaces and define the two boundary states $|A\rangle$ and $|B\rangle$ on the left and right edges of the cylinder, respectively, with the CFTs glued together by I .

Then the partition function on the cylinder is

$$Z_n^{cyl} = \sum_k \langle k | e^{-WH_n} | k \rangle \langle A | k \rangle \langle k | B \rangle \quad (152)$$

where the $|k\rangle$ represent the spectrum (which is assumed to be complete) of H_n . On the torus $|A\rangle = |B\rangle$ and

$$Z_n^{tor} = \sum_k \langle k | e^{-WH_n} | k \rangle \quad (153)$$

In the limit $W \gg 1$, the only state contributing is the ground state $|0\rangle$, and the term $\langle 0 | e^{-WH_n} | 0 \rangle$ is present in both cases. This is what yields the leading term of the entanglement entropy after taking the logarithm of the above expressions; therefore, it is the same despite the boundary conditions.

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